

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

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Revised use-cases for the FWCR Platform version Beta (PAR Cycle 1)

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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
AR	Action research
EEW	Earthquake early warning
FWCR	Forecasting, early warning, consequence prediction, response
OEF	Operational earthquake forecasting
PAR	Participatory action research
RAG	Red, amber, green
RRE	Rapid response to earthquakes
TB	Test bed
TRL	Technology readiness level
UC	Use case
WP	Work package

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1 INTRODUCTION

Action research (AR) is a form of research whereby researchers use the results of their research to act upon and change the situation being studied - and/or to inform the development of a solution/product. The action intervention is part of the research design: research that is limited to observation and the generation of theory is not AR. Participatory action research (PAR) is a form of AR¹ whereby the people or organisations who are the focus of the research (and for whom a solution/product is being developed) take an active part in the research process. They help researchers interpret and understand the situation, help shape the findings/solution and ultimately use the latter to inform their actions and decision-making.

Participatory action research is used in TURNkey as the primary research vehicle to link the needs of the end-users of the TURNkey system with those responsible for the design of the TURNkey system. In essence, PAR seeks to understand how the TURNkey system would be used in practical situations (from the perspective of the citizen, business organisations, critical infrastructure provider, and emergency responders) to improve resilience to an earthquake and to leverage this information to inform the TURNkey system design in a way that seeks to identify and address potential barriers to its use. Given this, PAR involves both potential end-users of a system as well as those responsible for its design and development. The original TURNkey concept model will be developed over three cycles over PAR, resulting in a final version of the system. This report presents the findings from PAR Cycle 1.

¹ Some early authors did not distinguish between AR and PAR, as they saw the use of participatory approaches as integral to AR (e.g., Lewin, 1946).

2 INTRODUCTION TO ACTION RESEARCH

2.1 Background on Action Research

The PAR approach in the TURNkey project draws on the work of Kurt Lewin, who used the term ‘action research’ to describe an approach to experimental research carried out in the field (rather than the laboratory) that viewed research subjects as active participants in the research process, rather than research objects to be studied (Lewin, 1946). In essence, Lewin argued that AR is a group activity that seeks to develop solutions to problems/issues through proactive dialogue with those responsible for delivering change (Adelman, 1993). In developing solutions AR is viewed as an iterative cyclical process – a journey (Figure 1) where group solutions are developed (planned), implemented (acted), monitored (evaluated) and reviewed (refined) as part of an iterative change programme Smith MK (1996; 2001, 2007, 2017). The AR cycle is repeated until an acceptable solution is achieved (convergence) or the journey is abandoned (divergence).

Figure 1 Schematic of an action research cycle (source: adapted from Smith, 1996; 2001, 2007, 2017)

In critiquing the development of AR, Smith (ibid) identified the critical requirements of each stage of the AR process. The first step is to clearly identify the objectives/goal for the study and the context in which the solution is located. This not only provides the start point for group discussions but also sets stopping criteria for the journey. With the objectives/goal and context established the action research team (researchers and end-users/stakeholders²) need to gather as much background information about the problem space/system and potential solutions as possible. This includes identifying the boundaries of the problem space/system (what is in the problem space and what are the constraints on the system, and more importantly what is outside the problem space) and reviewing past and existing solutions that

² In this report, the term ‘stakeholder’ refers to organizations with an interest in the TURNkey platform who contribute to the research project and may adopt the platform once finalised - whereas ‘end-users’ refers to the individual members of staff at those organizations (and beyond) who would interact with the platform.

are relevant to the problem space/system. This step includes reviewing theory that will be used to inform the situational context and the development of interventions (the fact-finding and planning stages) and in the interpretation and explanation of results (the evaluation phase) (Tripp, 2005). The initial planning stage to take the first action step (see Figure 1) involves a critical review of the project objectives/goal and the modification of the original objectives/goal if necessary. This evaluation stage is the first real collaborative activity for the AR team and it often requires the different team members to challenge their understanding of the problem space in response to other team members perspectives. The critical review stage also identifies misunderstandings (of terminology, objectives/goal, or theory) between AR team members and this may lead to a modification or refinement of the original project objectives/goals. At the end of the first planning stage, the AR team should be able to describe the problem space from multiple perspectives and be in a position to specify the requirements of the first action step.

The first action step entails the initial attempt at the development of a solution to the problem space. The solution needs to be developed in sufficient detail to allow the AR team to assess the degree to which it satisfies the project's objectives/goals, but not in so much detail as to limit future iterations of the solution by irreversible design decisions (e.g., theoretical perspectives, technological solutions, system constraints etc.). Achieving the balance between a solution capable of being effectively evaluated against the project objectives/goals and a solution that has multiple future development trajectories is difficult and requires significant skill on behalf of the AR team. The specific details of the evaluation process will vary depending upon the problem space. In general, the evaluation process seeks to test the solution against a range of end-user use-case scenarios with the view to establishing the degree to which the solution achieves its objectives/goal for each use-case scenario. At this stage it is possible, and indeed likely, that the solution will perform better against some use-case scenarios than others and this needs to be incorporated into the second planning stage (towards the second action step).

The main aim of the second planning stage is to reinforce the positive aspects of the solution, identifying the additional requirements of the solution/system (e.g., technical enhancements, changes in end-user practice/behaviour, economic and legal issues, culture etc.) needed to converge on the final solution; and address the negative aspects of the solution through either redesign or through an acceptance that the solution for these use-cases cannot be achieved at this stage (divergences). Divergences may occur as a consequence of technical, theoretical, economic, social, or legal limitations. The whole action cycle is then repeated for a third or even fourth time (although it is very unusual to go beyond 3 cycles) until a final solution is developed or the whole journey is abandoned.

Following completion of the AR's process, the AR team reflects on the whole AR journey to identify what change has occurred and to identify the learning that has emerged from the process and that could be used by others working in a similar problem space. In this way, AR contributes not only to a change in practice but also to the development of theory relating to the problem space which, in the case of TURNkey, means how EEW, OEF and RRE could enhance urban resilience. AR has been applied in a wide range of settings, such as operations management (Coughlan& Coughlan, 2002); education (Freire, 1996); and health-related research (Meyer, 2000).

2.2 Application of AR to sociotechnical systems

Action research when applied to developing sociotechnical solutions – such as TURNkey - seeks to adopt a holistic view in which contextual factors are considered as a fundamental aspect of the inquiry process (Ghaffarian, 2011). In essence, AR seeks to examine not just the technological system, or the social system, as independent, parallel systems but seeks to examine the impact that the interaction between the two systems have on emerging solutions (Ghaffarian, 2011). Further, in focusing on the interaction between systems, AR invariably results in a narrative discourse that presents solutions in the form of explanations of phenomena in context; where context is not considered fixed but is defined dynamically (Ghaffarian, 2011).

Tripp (2005) describes five AR modes. (They apply across all fields of enquiry – not just socio-technical systems). One of these models is technical AR, which seeks to enhance practice by applying an existing practice from elsewhere to a specific context. Another one is practical AR, which differs from technical AR, as it allows the AR team to interpret existing practice from elsewhere and develop their own version of the solution to fit their context. Political AR is about changing the system; or the constraints within which the system operates, which invariably means engaging with factors outside the immediate problem space (e.g., economic, legal, political etc) that affect it. Socially critical AR is a particular mode of political AR that is more concerned with what the system is, rather than with the constraints within the system, with a focus on such things as equality of opportunity, empowerment and communication. Emancipatory AR is another variant of political AR, which has the explicit aim of changing the status quo of individuals, groups or the whole system.

Tripp (2005) identified two components of an AR project; selection of the processes to be used in the field and the approach to the narrative that will be used to tell the story of the project and present the results. With regards to the AR processes, whilst these will vary depending upon the AR mode, they will generally draw on qualitative interactive methods (e.g., interviews, focus groups, workshops, observations, enquiry by design) supplemented where appropriate by quantitative methodologies (e.g., questionnaires, field experiments). With regards to the narrative, the most common approach is the use of an AR report (which is similar to the case study report) that provides a compelling narrative of the AR journey. The AR report needs to describe the objectives/goals of the project in sufficient detail to allow those outside of the project to understand the development of decisions taken at each AR stage (i.e., the different steps depicted in Figure 1) and during each AR cycle. It is also important that the AR report provides sufficient details of the situational context and current practices as well as a description of the planning, action and evaluation processes at each AR cycle and that at the end of the project it draws clear conclusions about the degree to which the final solution achieves the original project's objectives/goal.

2.3 Application of PAR to software and product development

AR has been used as part of a user-centred design approach for both software and product development. Lau (1997) did a comparative review between the use of different types of AR and more traditional social science system development methodologies across 30 information systems development projects published in academic literature. As with Tripp (2005), Lau (1997) identified a wide range of problem spaces to which an AR methodology was applied (from addressing specific practical problems through enhancement and communication projects, to developing change strategy programmes).

In those studies where AR was used as an information systems development methodology, its primary role was in defining end-user requirements, supporting systems analysis, and designing new systems solutions; all with the explicit input and collaboration of typical end-users. That said, Lau (ibid) noted the apparent reluctance amongst some information system developers to accept AR methodologies, related to loosely framed theoretical assumptions and flexible research approaches at the early stage of the system development. This led Lau (ibid) to develop an AR framework that could match the different approaches to AR with the complexity of information systems, technological interventions and organisational context. Lau's (ibid) framework identified 4 distinct dimensions (type and focus, underlying assumptions, processes and presentation) that guide the choice of which type of AR (action research, action science, participatory action research, and action learning) to apply to any given project. Based on Lau's framework, AR was identified as the most appropriate approach for the development of information systems seeking to use technological innovation to change practice. Lau's conclusions are consistent with those of De Villiers (2005), who also considered AR an appropriate development methodology for user-centric information systems where the technology interacts with complex social settings.

Ferrario et al. (2014) applied PAR principles to software engineering projects aimed at developing software for the 'social good'; including developing a crowdsourcing system supporting post-disaster management. As outlined above, participatory action research (PAR) is a form of AR that combines action research with participatory design. Central to PAR is collaboration with communities of enquiry. In PAR, the people or organisations for whom a software solution is being developed take an active part in the research process. They help researchers interpret and understand the situation, help shape the product and ultimately use the latter to inform their actions and decision-making. When using PAR, action and inquiry evolve over time to address the questions and issues that are significant to these research participants. After the initial planning, the PAR process goes through four iterative stages that (after n cycles) cumulate in deployment (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 The four stages in each PAR cycle (based on Interaction Design Foundation, 2021 and Corporate Planning Unit, Gov. of St. Lucia, 2016)

Ferrario et al. (ibid) developed a 'Speedplay' project management framework that integrated the principles of the PAR research spiral (see Figure 2) with user-centred design (design, develop, evaluate,

analyse) and an agile development methodology in an iterative process, to deliver a series of working prototypes against end-user specified needs. The Speedplay process model follows 4 stages:

- A preparation stage which combines existing theory with user needs and requirements, to test the original concept model and develop a design brief for product development;
- A design stage, where the technical feasibility of a prototype product solution is tested against end-user requirements; the design brief is modified to reflect user feedback and a second product solution is developed and tested;
- A build stage, in which iterative versions of working prototype products are developed and tested by end-users who provide feedback on product performance, including finalising requirements for full product development;

A sustain stage, where the full final working product is developed and implemented and where the lessons learnt throughout the Speedplay are collated and shared with others working in a similar problem space.

In software and product development, PAR is sometimes used to develop use cases (as is the case in TURNkey). This approach allows for end-user needs to inform design specifications (operational, socioeconomic, etc.) and to guide the development and testing of models and tools. Use cases are used to capture the user (actor) point of view while describing the functional requirements of the system. They describe the step by step process a user goes through to complete that goal using a software system. A use case is a description of all the ways an end-user wants to "use" a system. Use cases capture all the possible ways the user and system can interact that result in the user achieving the goal. They also capture all the things that can go wrong along the way that prevent the user from achieving the goal.

Brandt (2004) used the principles of PAR to explore the degree to which collaboration between stakeholders (designers, potential users, customers, sales and marketing professionals) could be incorporated into a user-centred design process for two projects undertaken by a large Danish corporation: the first looking at the role of customers and users as part of a product development team; the second looking at representing user needs in diagrammatic form throughout the design process. In both of these examples, Brandt explored the degree to which a problem space could be identified, and a solution developed through an iterative process of feedback (research) from users. Brandt concluded that such an approach could work if the feedback was structured and presented in a way that matched the work practices of design engineers.

In the first project, Brandt (2004) developed a PAR approach that facilitated a dialogue between users and the design team. Brandt achieved this through the use of a series of four structured workshops between the design team and potential users/customers. During each workshop, the design team presented their emerging solutions, along with any problems or questions that they had faced during the design of their solution. The solution was then jointly evaluated (against the original project objectives/goal) by the users/customers and design team and the design guidance amended to address any weaknesses in the solution. During the workshops, it became clear that just putting users/customers and designers into the same space did not in itself facilitate effective exchange of information. To support an effective exchange of information, Brandt identified the need for the PAR team to establish a common 'language' that spanned the different competencies and worldviews of the participants and allowed a dialogue that was not dominated by either technical or marketing arguments.

Another important consideration identified by Brandt (2004) was the need to provide the design team with the opportunity to take a step back and reflect on the wider issues raised in the workshops, and in particular to reflect on potential project creep resulting from changed expectations amongst the users/customers. For this reason, an internal workshop (without users/customers) amongst the design team was held to reflect on the outcomes from the customer/user workshops and deepen their understanding of the customers/users concerns and needs.

In the second project, Brandt (2004) applied PAR to cooperation between technical design teams from different organisations, rather than between design teams and end-users. Again, Brandt considered how to facilitate effective communication between different design teams, developing a series of diagrams as the basis to contextualise their emerging solutions from end-user and designers' perspectives. Although end-users were not directly involved in the development of the design representations, the design representations were nevertheless informed by visits to potential users at their places of work. The end-user perspectives were presented to the design teams as a diagram that superimposed use-cases onto a user base diagram (Figure 3 – left panel). The user base diagram comprised the x-axis which represented users as a continuum of potential users of the solution (rather than representing users as discrete entities) and the y-axis, which represented use levels that show how different users would interact with the system. To provide more specific information about the interaction between users and use levels, Brandt superimposed a series of use-cases onto the base diagram. Each use case represented a specific representation of how the system would be used in different circumstances. Figure 3 (right panel) zooms in to one of the three use cases depicted in the left panel, showing the individual steps of that use case.

In conclusion, whilst Brandt (2004) recognised that her application of PAR was not the classical approach proposed by Lewin in the 1940s she argued that PAR was an appropriate methodology for effectively engaging engineering designers with the needs of end-users in an iterative product development cycle that reflects the challenges of developing modern technological products.

Figure 3 The result of placing use-cases in the flexible basis diagram (adapted from Brandt, 2004)

The TURNkey project applied the principles of PAR described in this section to the development of the TURNkey **F**orecasting, **E**arly **W**arning, **C**onsequence Prediction, **R**esponse (FWCR) platform.

3 APPLICATION OF PAR TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TURNKEY PLATFORM

The TURNkey project is using PAR principles to guide the design, development and testing of the TURNkey FWCR platform (Figure 4). The PAR approach is using theory, refined through three iteration cycles of planning, implementation, reflection and review to integrate output from TURNkey’s technical WPs (WP3, WP4, WP5-in part) with end-user needs identified through TURNkey’s socio-economic WPs (WP1, WP2-in part, WP5-in part, WP7) and expressed as a set of end-user use-cases to guide the TURNkey FWCR platform development in WP6. The outputs from the three PAR cycles will be narrative reports that describe the research journey used to develop and test the use-cases along with any revisions needed to the use-cases identified during their evaluation.

Figure 4 TURNkey multidisciplinary methodology (source: TURNkey Grant Agreement)

The output from each PAR cycle will be fed into WP6, where the TURNkey FWCR platform will be refined to reflect the revised use cases. The original timescale envisaged feedback from the PAR cycles to WP6 at months 18, 24 and 32. However, due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the fieldwork associated with PAR, these timescales have been adjusted to reflect the practical issues associated with data collection from the Testbeds (TB) and researchers across the TURNkey project. Following discussions with the EC Project Officer through NORSAR, the timescale for delivery of the PAR cycle reports has been changed to months 22 (PAR Cycle 1 - this report), 28 (PAR Cycle 2) and 32 (PAR Cycle 3). The relationship between the PAR methodology and the development of the FWCR platform is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 relationship between the PAR cycles and the TURNkey FWCR development cycles

PAR cycle	Timeline	TRL	TURNkey FWCR platform
I	M18-M22	3-4	Version Beta
II	M23-M28	4	Version 2.0
III	M28-M32	5	Final Version

The PAR model (based on three cycles of PAR) used in the TURNkey project is shown in Figure 5. The first step of the PAR Cycle 1 is informed by the overall TURNkey project concept model. The concept model provides an overview of the goal of the TURNkey project, along with the theoretical

considerations that were used to shape the initial TURNkey FWCR platform solution. The TURNkey project concept model was developed through a series of meetings and workshops between the TURNkey partners to address the requirements of the original project brief set by the EU H2020 call document. Although technically this work occurred before the TURNkey project commenced, it is documented in this report as it provides the conceptual background to the PAR process model.

PAR Cycle 1 comprises four research stages:

1. Validation of the concept model from a technical and end-user (socio-economic) perspective:
 - a. Technical and socio-economic literature reviews of the concept model against theory and existing Earthquake Early Warning (EEW), Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF) and Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE) systems.
2. Testing of the conceptual model with representative end-user stakeholders:
 - a. Face-to-face and virtual workshops with end-user stakeholders involved in the TURNkey project, to develop typical use-cases on how the TURNkey platform could be integrated into their systems and processes to improve their resilience to an earthquake event,
3. Evaluation of the feedback from end-user stakeholders to inform the development of operational models and tools:
 - a. Virtual workshops with members of the technical TURNkey project WPs (3, 4, 5), to share the use-cases and consider the degree to which the technical solutions they were developing will satisfy end-user needs.
4. Reflection on the degree to which the TURNkey FWCR platform is achieving its stated goal (convergence) and identifying issues that need to be addressed during the next development cycle:
 - a. Virtual workshops and a questionnaire survey of TURNkey project members (researchers and end-user stakeholder representatives) to refine the TURNkey concept model to provide input into the development of the TURNkey FWCR platform version 2.0

Details of the results of the PAR Cycle 1 are given in the next section of this report.

Figure 5 The TURNkey PAR process model

4 OVERVIEW OF THE RESULTS FROM THE TURNKEY PAR ACTION RESEARCH CYCLE 1

This section of the report describes the processes and procedures used to facilitate each step of PAR Cycle 1 and the journey between steps. This section of the report does not reproduce the detailed analysis and findings of individual work tasks that form the basis of each step of the PAR cycle as these have been previously presented as individual TURNkey deliverables. Instead, this section of the report focuses on how the research findings were shared between the different steps of PAR Cycle 1 and amalgamated to develop the second TURNkey FWCR concept model.

4.1 The original TURNkey concept model

The TURNkey project was developed in response to the Horizon call H2020-SC5-17-2018 ‘Towards operational forecasting of earthquakes and early warning capacity for more resilient societies. The call document identified the need for multidisciplinary research to develop solutions that could support real-time seismic risk reduction across Europe, through practical applications of short-term forecasting, early warning methods, and loss reduction assessments for improving societal resilience. The call document also identified the need to integrate scientific research into effective procedures and improved decision-making schemes to respond to stakeholders’ needs and ultimately result in reduced human and economic losses associated with an earthquake event. In delivering an operational forecasting, earthquake early warning, consequence prediction and response system, the call also identified the need to develop effective communication between science and relevant users within the decision-making chain.

4.1.1 Initial development of the TURNkey concept model

Two project development workshops were held in Paris (February 2, 2018) and London (June 12, 2018) and email correspondence took place between potential project partners, to consider the requirements of the call brief and develop the TURNkey proposal. The original TURNkey proposal is described in detail in the Grant Agreement and summarised here to provide context for this section of the report.

The TURNkey project aims to undertake research to support the development of the TURNkey FWCR (forecasting - early warning - consequence prediction – response) platform that will integrate operational earthquake forecasting, earthquake early warning and rapid response to earthquakes into a cloud-based system to support the mitigation of earthquake risks across Europe (see Figure 12 for chronological sequence).

To address this aim, members of TURNkey developed the platform concept model. Figure 6 below shows this original TURNkey concept model, including the integration of its main system components. The figure depicts how existing and conventional seismological sensor networks (SN1), strong-motion networks (SN2), structural monitoring systems (SN3) smartphone-based (SN4) and eyewitness’ observations (SN5) will be improved and integrated into a single new platform, which provides EEW, RRE and OEF and focuses on providing actionable output for end-users. This original TURNkey concept model provided the research input into the first step of PAR Cycle I.

Figure 6 The original TURNkey concept model.

4.1.2 Developing a common understanding of the concept model amongst the TURNkey project development team

The PAR process started at the TURNkey project kick-off meeting held in Oslo (13-14 June 2019) where all project partners shared their understanding of the TURNkey concept model and of the working methods that would be used during the project. The WP presentations were followed by the first project General Assembly meeting. The kick-off workshop was attended by 44 participants and the General Assembly by 20 participants representing all but 1 of the project beneficiaries. Minutes of the meeting were sent to all participants.

All WPs presented their work programmes and answered questions about both technical content and operational issues; in particular about the integration/interactions between WPs and the role of the use cases generated through the PAR cycles. WP1 focussed on the role of PAR (as this methodology was

new to most of the participants) and the need for the research organisations involved with the project to consider themselves as active participants in the research process rather than passive providers of data and information. WP1 also highlighted the synergies between the four stages in each PAR cycle and the agile software development process being used by those partners developing the TURNkey FWCR platform (Figure 6). The first project General Assembly meeting confirmed the working and management arrangements for the project. Developing and enhancing the common understanding of the TURNkey concept model did not stop at the end of the kick-off meeting but formed an ongoing activity throughout WP1, informing the development of the end-user use-cases and forming a substantial contribution to deliverable D1.5.

4.2 PAR Cycle 1, Step 1– Validation of the TURNkey concept model

The first formal step of PAR Cycle 1 was validating the TURNkey concept model against the state-of-the-art in operational earthquake forecasting and earthquake early warning. Validation was done from a scientific, socio-economic and operational perspective focusing on Europe; the latter primarily through the integration of the TURNkey FWCR in supporting rapid response to earthquake events (RRE). Scientific validation, including the applicability of different scientific approaches to the European geological context, took place within the technical WPs (T3.1) and socio-economic validation took place in T1.1 and T3.1 (in part).

T1.1 performed a detailed literature review of OEF, EEW and RRE systems from a socio-economic perspective, focusing on the practical application of OEF, EEW and RRE systems to four stakeholder groups (citizens, emergency responders, critical infrastructure providers, and business organisations). This task identified the potential of the TURNkey FWCR platform to:

- Provide increased awareness/understanding of the impact of earthquakes on the stakeholder groups, including loss estimates;
- Improve public/occupational safety (including mental health);
- Support emergency and disaster management response plans, including business and community resilience plans;
- Provide autonomous or semiautonomous utility control;
- Reduce consequential damage to physical and operational assets and reduce recovery time; and
- Enhance post-earthquake safety assessments.

In realising the above opportunities, T1.1 identified a number of operational barriers and threats that needed to be considered during the development of the TURNkey FWCR platform. These include the need for:

- Metrics and outputs to be robust and reliable and to present risks and uncertainties in a way that is meaningful to end-user stakeholders (essentially in non-technical terms);
- End-user applications and guidance to reflect statutory regulations and governance frameworks within which the different stakeholder groups operate;
- Effective communication channels that not only present information in a useful way but are compatible with IT security and firewall systems;

- Longevity to provide end-users with the confidence to invest time and money in adopting the TURNkey FWCR platform and integrating it into their disaster management and resilience plans; and
- Systems to be designed to reflect the cultural and behavioural characteristics of the society within which they are located.

T3.1 also performed a detailed literature review and an analysis of the limits and potential applications of OEF, EEW and RRE to Europe, but from a technical perspective. The literature review evaluated different OEF and EEW methodologies against end-user requirements (from WP1) in Europe and other systems in operation around the world. T3.1 identified the Epidemic Type After-shock Sequence model (Ogata, 1998) as the most promising OEF approach for delivering end-user requirements of the TURNkey FWCR platform and confirmed the ability of probabilistic and evolutionary-based early warning systems as suitable methods to inform the EEW aspects of the TURNkey FWCR platform, more specifically, existing EEW algorithms for real-time event characterisation, such as PRESTo (Satriano et al., 2011). This said, T3.1 also identified the limitations with existing EEW systems including a lack of engineering-related risk and resilience metrics to effectively trigger EEW alerts in response to end-user requirements; identifying the need for engineering-based, application-specific models and tools to communicate risk and uncertainty. T3.1 also reviewed current approaches to RRE identifying the links between the generation of shake maps and the estimation of damage or losses through the use of exposure and vulnerability models. Again, T3.1 confirmed the scientific and technical validity of the TURNkey model.

The literature reviews effectively confirmed the validity of the original TURNkey FWCR concept model. Full details of the literature used to validate the TURNkey concept model can be found in deliverables D1.2 and D3.1.

The findings of the literature reviews were shared with technical WPs (2, 3, 4, 5, 6) through a series of ad-hoc virtual meetings between September 2019 and January 2020 and then at formal monthly WP meetings from January 2020. During these meetings, the various WP teams considered the implications of the findings from the validation process for the tools that they were developing for inclusion in the TURNkey FWCR platform. As the validation process confirmed the technical/scientific validity of the original approaches, the discussions tended to focus on the operational aspects required of the tools, and in particular how to effectively communicate risk and uncertainty to non-technical users as well as how to design outputs that could be integrated into existing stakeholder models and processes. The results of the dialogue within WP teams were early-stage design concepts for the development of the first set of end-user tools. These early design concepts in turn informed the development of a series of use cases that were used by researchers from WP1 to test business and critical infrastructure stakeholder reactions to the TURNkey FWCR platform. The results of this research are presented in Deliverable D1.4.

4.2.1 The first iteration of models and tools from WP6

Early work towards the (further) development of the TURNKey FWCR platform concept was conducted in early September of 2019 by Nutcracker Research, in partnership with NORSAR and B80. NORSAR and B80 developed a draft report on the system specifications, including archetypes of users of the platform (personas), module requirements, requirements vs personas, use cases, the application architecture and the user interface. This work was informed by a questionnaire sent to all

partners, which aimed to define as best as possible the population's needs and requirements for the TURNkey platform – and to define the TURNkey concept for citizens and first responders. This work informed PAR Cycle 1 research with civil protection, first responders and civilians. The results of this research are presented in Deliverable D1.3.

4.3 PAR Cycle 1, Testing of the first iteration of TURNkey operational models and tools with potential end-users

The second formal step of PAR Cycle 1 was testing the TURNkey concept model against the needs and requirements of potential end-users. As outlined above, this research was reported in D1.3 and D1.4. Whereas the former looked at civil protection, first responders and civilians, the latter looked at critical infrastructure providers and general business. D1.3 and D1.4 describe the first iteration of the TURNkey use cases. These use cases were revised at the end of PAR Cycle 1 (see Appendix A) and will be refined through further PAR cycles in WP2. Future iterations will be based on the more detailed proposition of the TURNkey FWCR platform that was developed during PAR Cycle 1 (see Figure 12).

Fieldwork for deliverable D1.3

For deliverable D1.3, three separate research projects were carried out with citizens and local stakeholders in Romania (TB1), Greece (TB4) and Italy (TB5). These three locations were chosen to capture a range of settings in terms of size, geographic and cultural characteristics and degree of seismic risk. Fieldwork was carried out between 27 November 2019 and 6 March 2020. Citizens attended 90-minute face-to-face discussion groups while local representatives from stakeholder organizations (e.g., civic protection) participated in one-to-one in-depth interviews. The research was conducted using recruitment questionnaires, interview guides and research stimuli for organisational stakeholders and discussion guides and research stimuli for citizens. These documents were translated by three local market research agencies who implemented the fieldwork.

The findings for deliverable D1.3 are based on an analysis of transcripts of the audio recordings of the interviews and discussion groups. A thorough content analysis was carried out with the transcripts, to identify common themes and insights from each location. D1.3 presents consistent themes across all three locations, as well as location-specific feedback. It provides key findings and consequent recommendations for the further development of the TURNkey platform.

Fieldwork for deliverable D1.4

The general business use cases developed for D1.4 during PAR Cycle 1 are based on a series of semi-structured interviews with key employees from a range of business types located in Iceland (TB3), France (TB2) and the Netherlands (TB6). These businesses included local production focused organisations that were part of global corporations; service delivery organisations that operated across geographical regions; business sector-specific organisations that collectively constitute significant employment in a region; and small business organisations.

During PAR Cycle 1, business end-users were presented with initial ideas on the potential of an FWCR platform for their organizations. A set of hypothetical scenarios was discussed with research participants. Furthermore, historic experiences of disasters were discussed as well as experiences with existing warning systems for natural hazards. In this context, current and past disaster risk management strategies were explored as well as reactions to the TURNkey proposition. Through these discussions,

the TURNkey research team has identified motivators and drivers that need to be exploited and barriers to usage that will need to be addressed to ensure that there is the desired response to the TURNkey solution.

Table 2 Hypothetical scenarios discussed with respondents.

What they would do if they were issued an alert 10 seconds before ground shaking occurred.
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What they would do if they were told with absolute certainty that significant ground shaking would occur after approximately 72 hours* 2. What they would do if they were told that the probability of ground shaking occurring after approximately 72 hours was high/medium/low.
*It was explained that this is currently impossible

Instead of seeking to identify specific attributes of particular systems, at that (early) stage in the PAR process, results from the interviews were analysed to identify generic ideas and concepts associated with applying EEW and OEF to day-to-day business activities. This is in keeping with the general principles of writing high-level use cases. The abstraction process drew together the initial in-field analysis of the research team undertaking the interviews (interviews were conducted by between one and four fieldworkers depending on location and timing). It presents business and critical infrastructure user goals that are relevant across Europe, despite different cultural, social, economic and physical environments, precisely because of their high level of abstraction, e.g., “reduce the risk of falling from height” and “reduce the risk of being trapped in confined spaces”. A more comprehensive content-based analysis of PAR interviews will be undertaken when a Beta test version of the FWRC platform is ready at the start of PAR Cycle 3 (see Figure 5). During PAR Cycle 2, a more specific iteration of the use cases will be rendered whereby context-specific factors will be taken into consideration, such as national regulations and regional disaster governance.

4.3.1 Key findings PAR Cycle 1 with civil protection, first responders and citizens

The concept description of the TURNkey proposition was presented to end-users based at stakeholder organizations (i.e., civil protection and emergency response) to get their reaction. Furthermore, these end-users were interviewed to assess how they view current earthquake (information) management and response approaches. Citizens were also asked for their perceptions on this point. Furthermore, they were asked to react to a selection of communication messages targeted at them, which TURNkey may facilitate. The findings are presented in deliverable D1.3 “Needs and expectations of citizens and first responders for the initial development of the TURNkey solutions and user-case scenarios”. This deliverable presents the needs of end-users based at stakeholder organizations and citizens in the field of earthquake information management and response. It looks hereby at the types and sources of information that end-users need. It is based on PAR with civil protection, emergency responders and citizens in Greece (TB4), Italy (TB5) and Romania (TB1).

The key insights from this research are:

Table 3 Information challenges in the immediate aftermath of an earthquake

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collecting and categorising the large volumes of information for use by responders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessing the damage done and setting priorities for intervention; and

- | |
|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining the reliability of received reports from citizens. |
|--|

Table 4 Important but unmet needs - stakeholders currently do not have access to tools that address these needs effectively

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A means to capture and integrate incoming data meaningfully and efficiently;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster mobilisation of emergency management resources (e.g., staff, vehicles, emergency generators, tents, signs, hospitals) using a centralised and partially automated alert system;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of the danger to frontline staff concerning, for example, aftershocks;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better interaction and integration of efforts across all mobilised institutions;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A smart operating system able to receive information about damage to infrastructure;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A digital communication system that can communicate automatically with citizens; and
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A more resilient communications network.

Table 5 End-users listed the following barriers to adopting TURNkey

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-existing platforms are likely to be in place and preferred. Integrating TURNkey with these systems may be challenging;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information communicated via a third-party platform may create security concerns;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Too many information sources may create redundant processes;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For many, a central authority will need to sign-off on take-up; and
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any required training entails costs.

Amongst citizens, various message types were tested for appeal and relevance. Before an earthquake, OEF messaging would be appreciated as it empowers individuals and prompts them to search for information on what to do in case of an earthquake and plan ahead. However, EEW messages are less appealing as they give little or no time to act.

Table 6 In the aftermath of an earthquake, citizens would like to have information on the following:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The nearest earthquake-safe assembly points and viable routes to get there;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The condition of key infrastructure. e.g., hospitals;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whether water/gas/electricity can be used etc.;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locations where temporary housing is being set up;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information on the magnitude, location etc. of the earthquake;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which buildings to avoid/are at risk of collapse following the earthquake; and
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to locate essential items such as water, food, and blankets.

Importantly messages of ‘togetherness’ and solidarity are effective for community cohesion during recovery. Two types of messages were identified within this theme:

- Official messages that demonstrate a commitment to reconstruction and aid for all; and
- The promotion of volunteer effort, encouraging as many as possible to participate.

4.3.2 Key findings: PAR Cycle 1 with critical infrastructure and general business

To understand the practical/operational requirements that general businesses and critical infrastructure providers have of the TURNkey platform, between February and May 2020, a series of semi-structured interviews were conducted with key employees from a range of business types located in France (TB2), Iceland (TB3), Greece (TB5) and The Netherlands (TB6). This research built on face-to-face interviews that were conducted in 2019 by TURNKey researchers with earthquake experts in Japan and New Zealand. Fieldwork in TB3 was conducted in person. However, due to the COVID pandemic, fieldwork in the other testbeds had to be conducted online. Interviews were conducted with key staff at a range of organisations, including local production providers that were part of global corporations; service delivery organisations that covered wide areas marked by different geographies; business sector-specific organisations that collectively constitute significant employment in a region; and small business organisations. (These categories overlap).

During the interviews, interviewees were asked about their past experiences of earthquake disasters (and other disasters triggered by natural hazards) as well as their experiences of existing warning systems for these hazards. In this context, current and past disaster risk management strategies were explored as well as reactions to the TURNkey proposition. Through these discussions, researchers identified motivators and drivers that need to be exploited and barriers to take up that need to be addressed to ensure that there is the desired response to the TURNkey solution. The use cases show how the TURNkey platform, through OEF, EEW and RRE, affects resilience in urban settings (Figure 7). See deliverable D1.4 for the original use cases or the revised version in Appendix A. A selection of findings is presented in Figures 8, 9 and 10 below. Deliverable D1.4 approaches business-centric RRE as the result of more effective business continuity and disaster management planning, made possible by EEW and OEF. As such, the RRE use cases listed under table 10 list activities enabled by EEW and OEF.

Figure 7 The use cases show how the TURNkey platform improves resilience via EEW, OEF and RRE

Findings – OEF selected use cases (see D1.4 for full report)		
Personal safety	To reduce the risk to employee safety due to ground shaking	Rescheduling of non-time-critical tasks during periods of high earthquake risk
		Senior management review of the risks associated with continuing time-critical tasks during periods of high earthquake risk
Business disruption	Activation of off-site backup	Testing of physical off-site backup systems during a period of high earthquake risk
		Testing of data off-site backup systems during a period of high earthquake risk
Joint planning	Reduce the impact of operational downtime on customers	Activation of disaster planning committee to test disaster management and business continuity plans during a period of high earthquake risk

Figure 8 Findings of selected OEF use cases for critical infrastructure and general business

Findings – EEW selected use cases (see D1.4 for full report)		
Use Case	Goal	Use Case Instance
Personal safety	To reduce the risk of objects falling from height due to ground shaking	Automatic alert to employees working at height to check equipment safety lines and to those managing ground-level exclusion zones to ensure that zones are clear
		Automatic alert to employees operating lifting gear to return any objects being lifted to the ground
Community safety	To avoid derailment of a high-speed train with consequent injuries to people (passengers and staff)	Automatic alert to initiate safety protocols to reduce the speed of trains on open tracks
		Automatic alert to initiate safety protocols to either prevent a train entering tunnel or expedite a train exiting a tunnel
Minimise damage to critical systems	To reduce potential damage to critical business systems as a result of ground shaking	Automatic alert to operators of critical production systems to place the systems in a 'safe mode' during ground shaking
		Manual alert to operators of critical production systems to place the systems in a 'safe mode' during ground shaking

Figure 9 Findings of selected EEW use cases for critical infrastructure and general business

Findings - Business/CI centric RRE comes as a consequence of OEF and EEW	
Improved employee safety allowing rapid return to work	Enhanced workplace health and safety checks, including activation of temporary storage at times of increased risk
	Re-scheduling of potentially dangerous work tasks during periods of increased risk
	Stopping of dangerous work and rapid protection of workforce on receipt of a EEW alert
Minimise damage to critical systems allowing quick restart	Set up automated switch to fail-safe mode of vulnerable critical assets upon receipt of ground shaking alert.
	Automated shutdown of hazardous systems on receipt of EEW alert mimising potential damage from cascading events (e.g. fire)
Reduce disruption to business systems	Early activation of disaster management plans including off-site back-up facilities and repair/response teams placed on standby
	Joint planning with supply chain and re-scheduling / early deployment of critical logistics at time of increased risk

Figure 10 Findings of selected OEF and EEW use cases for business-centric RRE

4.3.3 The general usefulness of the TURNkey concept model

The TURNkey concept description was deemed well-placed to meet a number of end-user needs in the areas of disaster management and business continuity. The platform features that are deemed particularly relevant by civil protection and first responders are the earthquake dashboard situation report, two-way communication and infrastructure management features. To critical infrastructure and general business, EEW alerts and short-term OEF lay at the heart of all use cases. There is potential for TURNkey to offer end-users a number of benefits, which help them meet their objective of preparing and responding effectively. Most of these centre around being given accurate and timely information in a way that requires minimal operational resources to process. However, it is important that the platform be compatible with existing operational protocols and legacy systems that are in place. While end-users would welcome more accurate information, it is critical that this is delivered in a way that integrates seamlessly with current systems, presents information in a way that facilitates a quick and accurate assessment of intervention priorities and is accessible to non-technical operatives. As the platform outputs are developed, further research will be carried out amongst these end-users to determine whether these are in line with their expectations and whether these outputs would, indeed, help render operational planning and management more effective in the immediate aftermath of an earthquake.

The use-cases developed during PAR Cycle 1 inform PAR Cycle 2. During this second cycle, the use cases will be further developed through meetings and interviews with end-user representatives and other TURNkey WP/TB team leaders, Testbed teams to facilitate local reflection and review of the prototype TURNkey FWCR. As with PAR Cycle 1, during PAR Cycle 2 the use-cases will be revised in light of this review to address any weaknesses in the TURNkey FWCR platform. The revised use-cases will be applied in other WPs to produce the second version of the TURNkey FWCR platform. After that, Version 2.0 of the TURNkey FWCR platform will be further reviewed and the final use-cases developed to address any weaknesses in the TURNkey FWCR platform. During PAR Cycle 3, the Beta version of the TURNkey platform will be tested with end-users. This will feed into the development of end-user tools and guidance.

4.4 PAR Cycle 1, step 3: development of the first set of TURNkey models and tools

To operationalize the OEF, EEW, RRE features outlined under Figure 6 on the basis of the use cases developed under deliverables D1.3 and D1.4, researchers conducted online discussions with researchers and developers from the TURNkey WPs. These discussions aimed at developing a common understanding of the TURNkey proposition: the design and operational expectations of the TURNkey platform. The discussions explored how the use cases could be operationalized to 1) put it to potential end-users for their input and feedback during PAR Cycle; 2) support the efforts of WP6 to integrate all EEW/OEF/RRE tools into the FWCR platform; and 3) provide an outline of how TURNkey shapes community resilience, using systems theory. To this end, representatives from the WPs were asked for input on the points below. They did so in writing, during small online meetings (discussions were held with all WPs separately) and during a collective meeting with representatives from all WPs at the end of this process.

- What will TURNkey deliver in terms of OEF, EEW and RRE?
- When does it issue alerts? What are the thresholds? How will they be displayed graphically, e.g., will they be based on the established traffic light alert system: red, amber, green (RAG)?
- What are the inputs for OEF, EEW and RRE?
- What are the outputs during OEF, EEW and RRE?
- How do the different sub-systems/modules contribute to the whole?
- Which sub-systems interact?
- What are the platform's boundaries?
- How would a malfunction in one sub-system affect other subsystems - and the whole?

The purpose of these discussions was to explore the scientific, technical, operational and governance challenges that pose barriers to achieving the TURNkey proposition. The goal was to explore how these challenges could be addressed and what TURNkey could realistically deliver. These points will be taken up and developed further after PAR Cycle 2 with end-users at stakeholder organizations. The section below outlines the views of the different WPs on what TURNkey will realize by the end of the project. Not all meetings covered all phases of the TURNkey chronology (i.e., long term risk assessment, OEF, EEW and RRE) as some WPs preferred to only give feedback on phases that fell within their own area of responsibility. The views expressed below are at times in conflict with each other. These conflicts were resolved during the collective meeting, which was held after the individual meetings. The result was the revised conceptual model depicted in Figure 11.

WP3 online meeting: 08.05.2020

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of long-term risk assessment?

Views expressed by participants: We have not promised long-term OEF in the TURNkey proposal. Long term models and tools could be added to TURNkey as background input, but these tools should not necessarily be opened up to the outside world. If these tools are presented to end-users, as something they can use themselves, TURNkey needs to make sure they work perfectly. Short-term OEF (which was promised) is different from long term analyses.

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of OEF?

Views expressed by participants: We can use OEF for both aftershocks and foreshocks, but with different forecast periods. The ETAS model can be run looking at short periods (days) during aftershocks and long periods (e.g., a month) during foreshocks. We can use OEF for time-dependent seismicity and daily PSHA in terms of ETAS for Iceland (TB3) and in terms of non-seismic indicators for the Bucharest Testbed. The OEF system could provide updated seismological inputs for the EEW algorithms. We can provide a dashboard showing risk levels and guidance on corresponding suitable actions for end-users. OEF for aftershocks is of limited use to end-users (they already have procedures in place). Regarding how to phrase things: OEF is neither 'robust' nor 'reliable' due to the great level of uncertainty. We should be careful about stakeholders' expectations when using such a concrete phrase.

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of EEW?

Views expressed by participants: Provide warning a few seconds before an earthquake to stakeholders/organizations/government/public.

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of RRE?

Views expressed by participants: Provide spatially distributed intensity and loss maps around the earthquake epicentre a few minutes after shaking happens and update these maps over time (hours), using instrumental and human feedback. Provide loss metrics (fatality, injuries, structure/non-structure/infrastructure damage etc) to related authorities /first responders /and other stakeholders to manage their actions.

WP4 online meeting: 04.05.2020

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of OEF?

Views expressed by participants: In the mobile testbed (TB8), real-time on-site monitoring is being implemented using temporary instrument installations. This may facilitate early warning. However, OEF requires a lot of data. A major investment is required before pre-main event OEF can be delivered. TURNkey could deliver guidelines, but pre-main event OEF may be beyond the scope of the project. However, when it comes to OEF for time-dependent aftershocks the science is more ready. As such, OEF for aftershocks may be within the TURNkey proposition.

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of EEW?

Views expressed by participants: this depends on the geological and seismological context, the presence of instrumental data, seismic networks etc. There is, for example, little scope for EEW in the Pyrenees but it could be effective in for example Bucharest.

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of RRE?

Views expressed by participants: Maps and indicators related to the earthquake impact will be rapidly generated, accounting for field observations (shake-maps from WP3, but also structural health monitoring of specific structures, or eye-witness accounts of damage). Maps will indicate probabilities of damage (different damage states), at least at the level of city districts or building blocks. Estimation of social losses (casualties, population in need of healthcare and/or shelter) will also be provided. Regarding infrastructure systems, indicators related to the system performance will be provided (road accessibility, port functionality, hospital availability, etc.).

WP5 online meeting: 14.05.2020

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of EEW?

Views expressed by participants: EEW should trigger alerts that are optimized for the needs of - and are understandable to- a given end-user so that clear preventative actions can be taken to mitigate the impact of an event. Using earthquake engineering expertise, fragility and vulnerability/damage-to-loss models for target structure/infrastructure should be combined with ground motion amplitude predictions, to determine end-user focused estimates of damage and loss. Multi-criteria decision-making tools should then be used to determine whether or not to trigger an alert, accounting for end-user preferences towards expected losses. Since the engineering models represent a static piece of information (concerning the EEW-based hazard estimates), damage/loss predictions can be pre-computed offline for all possible ground motion amplitude estimates and then simply retrieved in real-time, for rapid decision-making.

WP6 online meeting: 24.04.2020

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of long-term risk assessment

Views expressed by participants: The term “long-term OEF” is unfortunate and should not be used. Long-term OEF is a standard risk assessment. TURNkey will model data, run static scenarios to inform long-term disaster risk reduction planning and urban planning. TURNkey will bring everything together in one platform. It will not create something new for long-term analyses but use existing tools/models. If end-users want to do a long-term risk assessment, they should be able to use TURNkey. Besides, long term models are needed for rapid response. For the end-user: they should be able to visualise the background information that is available for their region.

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of OEF?

Views expressed by participants: TURNkey should focus on short-term hazard changes (i.e. aftershock sequences) by size and region. Warn stakeholders of changes in seismic hazard conditions to enable short-term preventative action (e.g., informed by cost-benefit analysis).

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of EEW?

Views expressed by participants: EEW should be adapted to local legislation. It should be delivered directly to the governance body in charge (e.g., civil protection) and critical infrastructure providers. The general public may get information via an app or through the website (that an earthquake is coming, along with a standard safety instruction). EEW should focus on the risk to human life - not on preventing economic loss. Within seconds, the magnitude, location and intensity of the earthquake would be shared with all end-users. An alarm would be sent to critical infrastructure providers (e.g., hospitals) with location, magnitude and ground-shaking contour data. Automated systems (e.g., at critical infrastructures) would receive information to trigger automated actions (if required).

What should TURNKEY deliver in terms of RRE?

Views expressed by participants: A damage map would be made available to responders showing building damage, the level of functionality and the condition of lifeline infrastructure (such as roads), to enable them to plot safe routes to the affected areas. They would also receive information on the probable number of casualties (based on the probability of buildings having collapsed) as well as the probable number of people requiring shelter. Information would be sent on how many shelters would

need to be built (and where) and how many beds there would be available in hospitals (again based on probable level of damage). Information would be sent on where the safe zones would be. This impact information, however, should not be shared with the general public (to avoid panic).

4.5 PAR Cycle 1, the evaluation stage– reflection on the use cases and evolving prototype

PAR Cycle 1 concluded with a collective reflection of the use cases and the evolving prototype. This is step 4 in Figure 5. As outlined, reflection is a central component of PAR. The collective reflection carried out at the end of PAR Cycle 1 informs the 2nd version of the conceptual tools and models for TURNkey. This reflection took place over three events. It started with the consortium meeting on 22.09.2020, during which participants discussed the evolving TURNkey platform prototype during its different planned stages: revised concept model (M18), Beta version (M24) and final version (M32). They discussed end-users, functionalities, information flows and community resilience models. Finally, a mock-up of the graphical user interface was shown and discussed. This was followed in February 2021 by a situational analysis questionnaire, which aimed to identify practical opportunities and barriers to the implementation of the TURNkey system. The findings of this questionnaire mark the start of PAR Cycle 2 and will be presented in deliverable D2.8. Finally, a use case review meeting was held on 09.02.21 with researchers and designers from the TURNkey WPs. This meeting aimed to review the use cases developed for civil protection, first responders, critical infrastructure and general businesses presented in deliverables D1.3 and D1.4. The purpose of this discussion was to assess what TURNkey could realistically deliver and to adjust the use cases accordingly. The focus was on key features that use cases had in common, grouped by EEW for critical infrastructure and general business (Table 7), OEF for critical infrastructure and general business (Table 8) and EEW and RRE for civil protection and first responders (Tables 9 to 11). During this workshop, TURNkey researchers looked both at what was technically feasible and at what falls within the realm of the TURNkey proposition. Both were rated on a scale from 0 (impossible) to 5 (definitely). In-between scores for technical feasibility indicate that, whilst development is not impossible, there are (minor/major) scientific or engineering challenges that need to be overcome. In-between scores for 'fit' with the TURNkey proposition (i.e., whether TURNkey will realize these features, either directly or indirectly, by the end of the project) indicate that the features will only be partially realized by the end of the project.

Table 7 EEW use cases critical infrastructure and general business

Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this directly or indirectly?	Notes
EEW/ RRE	Minimise direct damage to critical systems & Limit injuries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey issues ground shaking alert directly to critical infrastructure provider / general business 	5	5 (indirectly)	Not possible in all locations
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal alerts carried by individual workers, working in dangerous locations (e.g., at height, in confined spaces, at risk from falling objects) Systems that control vulnerable or dangerous assets (to automatically stop them or switch them to fail-safe mode) Tailored to specific organisations 	5	0 future - not during the project	Alternative: TURNkey app could also be used by employees
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey dashboard informs managers of automated actions by in-house systems triggered by TURNkey EEW alerts 	5	0 future - not during the project	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey issues the 'all clear' (i.e., no impending aftershocks) [based on OEF for aftershocks] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workers can evacuate and report to their managers Systems can be restarted 	0	0	Not possible. Instead, notification as part of OEF: 'Did the earthquake happen?' Y/N (with probabilities). If Y - regular updates regarding aftershocks with probabilities assigned

		• Technical guidance on the integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with in-house s	5	Future – not during the project	
		• Guidance on how to incorporate EEW in disaster management and business continuity plans	5	Future – not during the project	
				0 = No, impossible 5 = Yes, definitely	

Table 8 OEF use cases critical infrastructure and general business

Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this directly or indirectly?	Notes
OEF	Improve employee safety & Reduce disruption to business & Minimise cascading risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey notifies critical infrastructure provider / general business of changes in seismic hazard in the location of its assets (push and/or pull notifications). 	5	Indirectly 5	Requires civil protection buy-in
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey notifies critical infrastructure provider / general business of changes in risk to its assets (push and/or pull notifications) 	5	Indirectly 5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey provides easy to read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG alert system - red, amber, green) The organization would consider the forecast against specific operational and business risk scenarios when deciding what action to take (if any) 	5	Indirectly 5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey provides easy to read forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., “red forecast for the next 48 hours”) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Managers can reschedule non-critical tasks Repair teams, back-up systems, portable logistics equipment can be put on stand-by 	2	0 (maybe in future)	No end time can be given. Instead: real-time updates during the aftershock phase.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TURNkey provides critical infrastructure provider / general business and selected critical business partners with OEF alerts 	5	0 - Maybe in the future	

For all features listed in Table 8, the extent to which TURNkey can realize them depends on the networks that are in place, which feed the platform in real time. This also requires consistency in the types of data.

Table 9 EEW and RRE use case civil protection and first responders – alert first responders

Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this directly or indirectly?	Notes
EEW /RRE	Headquarters can safeguard first responders' lives by alerting them to dangerous conditions on the ground.	A platform for two-way communication between headquarters and the field that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables first responders on the ground to assess the degree of danger before accessing collapsed structures 	0	0	Not part of TURNkey
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables first responders on the ground to leave the building if an aftershock is anticipated 	2	2	This is quantified using OEF, rather than EEW/RRE. Feasibility study in Mobile Testbed - TB8
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables first responder decision-makers to communicate instructions aimed at safeguarding rescuers' lives 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables first responder decision-makers to monitor rescuers' wellbeing during operations 	5	3-5	The EEW app 'Safety Check' supports sending data about damage during RRE.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> incorporates early warning notifications 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> incorporates aftershock information 	5	5	This relates to OEF, rather than EEW/RRE
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> has the feature 'rescuer status' 	5	3 – 5	

		The platform should support the two-way sharing of information on	5	5 (through the app)	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> impacted buildings 	5	5 (through the app)	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> other critical infrastructure 	2	2	The two-way sharing of information on incoming aftershocks is technically challenging and will not be realized before the end of the project
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> incoming aftershocks 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> rescuer wellbeing 			0 = No, impossible 5 = Yes, definitely

Table 10 EEW and RRE use case civil protection and first responders - more effective data management

Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this directly or indirectly?	Notes
EEW /RRE	Decision-makers and communicators cut down on time and effort used to collate and process multiple and fragmentary data inputs.	A dashboard for first responders that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> has an 'earthquake cockpit situation report' feature 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> rapidly populates with information from multiple sources (social media, network accessibility etc) 	5	4 – 5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> presents information that is comprehensive and continuously updated 	5	4-5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> presents information in a way that facilitates a rapid understanding of the current situation 	5	3-5	Requires trial and error with end-users
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> presents information in a way that enables decision-makers to prioritise interventions and allocate resources accordingly 	5	3– 5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> makes it possible to query information and drill down for detail on a specific area, element of infrastructure and critical building 	5	0 - for future	Case dependent. Requires satellite structural health monitoring. Can be done in advance. Not for every single building - maybe at the level of the neighbourhood.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables users to relay information to decision-makers within their organization and other institutional users. 	5	3-5	Features: user can provide information. Email options.

	End users responsible for alerting key actors cut down on time and resources required to do so.	An automated real-time alert registry/database for contact points at third party organizations and key personnel that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> is linked to TURNkey features such as 'automatic notification' or 'call to action'. 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> end-users can populate / modify beforehand 	5	5	
			0 = No, impossible 5 = Yes, definitely		

Table 11 EEW and RRE use case civil protection and first responders - improved coordination

Phase	End-user goals	What is needed	Technical Feasibility	Can/will TURNkey deliver this directly or indirectly?	Notes
EEW /RRE	First responders and external organizations involved in the response improve their coordination towards a more effective intervention.	An information/communication platform that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> allows all users to input information (rescue information) 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> allows all users to access information 	5	5	Depends on decision-maker
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> alerts external organizations 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> has a 'safe areas identification' feature 	5	5	Depends on input – before and during the crisis
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> has a 'damage assessment' feature 	5	5	Depends on input – before and during the crisis
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> allows for eye witness information input (TURNkey and third-party apps) first responders have their own app. 	5	5 indirectly	Via the app for the general public). Validated beforehand by decision-makers (e.g., civil protection).
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> shows the evolution of the rescue operation 	5	1-2	Not the focus of TURNkey
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables external organizations to monitor the situation 	5	5	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enables the sending of instructions to external organizations 	5	5	
				The platform should include information on	5

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> location and extent of damages, affected areas and infrastructure viability 			
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> emergency intervention sites and progress on the response efforts at those locations 	5	3-4	This will be partially/mostly realized
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ongoing prioritisation exercises of different emergency interventions during a response 	5	1-2	Not the focus of TURNkey. Simulations give an overview of what could happen.
				0 = No, impossible 5 = Yes, definitely	

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS – REVISED USE-CASES

5.1 Key lessons from the PAR Cycle 1

PAR Cycle 1 shows that the original TURNkey concept model presented in Figure 6 is valid and could form the basis of a multi-sensor information system enabling earthquake forecasting, early warning and rapid response actions to support improved earthquake resilience across Europe. Figure 11 below depicts the high-level TURNkey proposition, developed in May 2020. The theoretical basis of the tools to support the TURNkey platform is scientifically sound and can be integrated into an end-user platform that can support most elements of the use cases identified in WP1. Not all features desired by end-users were scientifically feasible or will be realized by the end of the project. As a result, some changes were made to specific use cases. The next section summarizes the main changes made to the use cases. The revised use cases are included in Appendix A. Figure 12 shows the revised use cases mapped against the OEF, EEW, and RRE timeline.

5.1.1 Changes made to use cases

Three of the EEW and RRE use cases for civil protection, first responders and citizens have been amended. The use case ‘Capturing and integrating multiple sources of information meaningfully and effectively’ (Appendix A, Table 13) was amended to reflect the following: whilst it is technically feasible to provide a platform feature that makes it possible to drill down for detail on a specific area, element of infrastructure or critical building, this is case dependent and requires satellite structural health monitoring. It could be done in advance at the level of the neighbourhood – but not for every single building. This feature will not be realized before the end of the project (see Table 10). The use case ‘Improved visibility of danger to first responders in the field’ (Appendix A, Table 15) has been amended to reflect the fact that it is not yet scientifically possible to alert first responders on the ground of incoming aftershocks (see Table 9). A feasibility study is currently being conducted in the mobile testbed, TB8. However, TURNkey scientists currently rate the scientific/engineering feasibility of realizing aftershock alerts to first responders via the platform as 2 (on a scale of 0 to 5, whereby 0 is impossible and 5 is definitely). Finally, the use case ‘Better communication and co-ordination of efforts across all institutions involved in the response phase’ (Appendix A, Table 16) has been amended to reflect the following: whilst feasible from a scientific/engineering perspective, it is not part of TURNkey’s focus to show the evolution of the rescue operation or support prioritisation exercises (see Table 11).

Table 12 below summarizes the changes made to the EEW and OEF use cases for critical infrastructure and general business. Except for instance 2 (manual control) of the use case ‘Minimise direct damage to critical system’ (Appendix A, Table 29), all EEW use cases require the integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems. TURNkey scientists rate the scientific/engineering feasibility of realizing such integration as 5 (on a scale of 0 to 5, whereby 0 is impossible and 5 is definitely). However, TURNkey will not facilitate the optional integration of EEW alerts with in-house systems during the project. As such, all EEW use cases have been labelled ‘future use cases’ (except for the use case presented in Appendix A, Table 29). All OEF use cases are centred on TURNkey being able to issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., “red forecast for the next 48 hours”). However, giving a timeframe with an end time is not yet possible scientifically. For the same reason, TURNkey can’t issue the “all clear” after ground shaking. Instead, TURNkey can issue real-time updates

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of changes in seismic hazard and risk to business assets for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties. The EEW and OEF use cases have been amended accordingly. See Appendix A for full detail on the revised use cases.

Table 12 Summary of changes made to use cases – business and critical infrastructure

Use Case	Goal	Use Case Instance – Original (D1.4)	Change March 2021
EEW			
Personal Safety	To reduce the risk of falling from height due to ground shaking.	Automatic alert to an employee working at height to check safety equipment and evacuated possible. Employee awaits the ‘all clear’.	<p>TURNkey will NOT facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems as part of this project. It is technically feasible – and may be done in the future after the project.</p> <p>As such, there will be NO integration with personal alerts carried by individual workers. However, they could use the TURNkey app (designed for first responders).</p> <p>The TURNkey dashboard will NOT issue the ‘all clear’.</p> <p>Instead, TURNkey will provide</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Notification: did the earthquake happen Y/N (with probabilities) 2) If Y - regular updates re: aftershocks with probabilities assigned (part of OEF) <p>Managers have to issue the ‘all clear’ based on this information.</p>
	To reduce the risk of being trapped in confined spaces due to ground shaking	Automatic alert to an employee working in a tunnel to move to the tunnel exit immediately. Employee awaits the ‘all clear’.	
		Automatic alert to an employee working in a crawl space under heavy equipment/machinery to exit the crawl space. Employee awaits the ‘all clear’.	
	To reduce the risk of objects falling from height due to ground shaking	Automatic alert to employees working at height to check equipment safety lines and to those managing ground-level exclusion zones to ensure that zones are clear. Employee awaits the ‘all clear’.	
		Automatic alert to employees operating lifting gear to return any objects being lifted to the ground. Employee awaits the ‘all clear’.	
To reduce the risk of personal injury caused by handling dangerous equipment during ground shaking (e.g., chain saws)	Automatic alert to an employee/contractor handling dangerous equipment (e.g., chain saws) to switch off said equipment. Employee awaits the ‘all clear’.		
Community safety	To reduce the risk to the local community of toxic substance spillage due to ground shaking.	Automatic alert to initiate safe shut off of on-site storage and distribution systems. Operator awaits the ‘all clear’.	<p>TURNkey will NOT facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems as part of this project. It is technically feasible – and may be done in the future after the project.</p>
	To avoid derailment of a high-speed train with consequent	Automatic alert to initiate safety protocols to reduce the speed of trains on open tracks. Operator awaits the ‘all clear’.	

	damage to people (passengers and staff) (3 instances)	Automatic alert to initiate safety protocols to either prevent a train from entering a tunnel or expedite a train exiting a tunnel. Operator awaits the 'all clear'.	As such, there will be NO integration with systems that control vulnerable or dangerous assets. The TURNkey dashboard will NOT inform managers of automated actions by in-house systems triggered by TURNkey EEW alerts – nor will TURNkey issue the 'all clear'.
	To avoid gas leakage and consequent explosions	Automatic alerts to initiate safety protocols to either prevent a train from entering a bridge or expedite a train exiting a bridge. Operator awaits the 'all clear'.	
		Automatic alert to gas supply companies for a manual decision on the activation of safety protocols to protect the gas distribution network. Operator awaits the 'all clear'.	Instead, TURNkey will provide
Minimise Damage to Critical Systems	To reduce potential damage to critical business systems as a result of ground shaking	Automatic alert to operators of critical production systems to place the systems in a 'safe mode' during ground shaking. Operator awaits the 'all clear'.	1) Notification: did the earthquake happen Y/N (with probabilities) 2) If Y - regular updates re: aftershocks with probabilities assigned (part of OEF) Managers have to issue the 'all clear' based on this information.
		Automatic alert to turn support systems (e.g., power supply, raw material supply etc) into a 'safe mode' during ground shaking. Operator awaits the 'all clear'.	
		Manual alert to operators of critical production systems to place the systems in a 'safe mode' during ground shaking. Operator awaits the 'all clear'.	
OEF			
Personal safety	To reduce the risk to employee safety due to ground shaking	Rescheduling of non-time-critical tasks during periods of high earthquake risk	TURNkey will NOT issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., "red forecast for the next 48 hours"). Giving a timeframe is not yet possible scientifically.
		Senior management review of the risks associated with continuing time-critical tasks during periods of high earthquake risk	
Enhanced H&S	To reduce the risk to employee safety due to ground shaking	Increased regularity of health and safety checks of critical areas during a time of high earthquake risk to ensure all health and safety protocols were fully activated	Instead, TURNkey will issue real-time updates of changing seismic hazard.
		Temporary redeployment of warehouse storage; moving items stored at height to ground level during a time of high earthquake risk	

Business Disruption	Repair teams on standby	Critical teams (e.g., maintenance teams, logistics teams, security teams etc) needed to ensure a rapid response to an earthquake are placed upon standby during a period of high earthquake risk	
	Activation of off-site backup	Testing of physical off-site backup systems during a period of high earthquake risk	
		Testing of data off-site backup systems during a period of high earthquake risk	
	Redeployment of temporary logistics	Temporary logistics (e.g., backup generators) would be deployed (from storage facilities) to local sites to ensure continuity of service during a period of high earthquake risk	
Rescheduling of business activities that are highly susceptible to ground shaking	To prevent loss or damage, senior business managers and/or specialist subcontractors responsible for activities that are highly susceptible to ground shaking (e.g., involving equipment that measures vibrations) decide whether to go ahead or reschedule said activities, based on OEF.		
Joint planning	Reduce the impact of operational downtime on customers	Activation of the disaster planning committee (e.g., business, critical infrastructure, emergency responders etc) to test disaster management and business continuity plans during a period of high earthquake risk	TURNkey will provide OEF to critical infrastructure providers / general businesses (indirectly via civil protection) but NOT to the <i>critical business partners</i> of those organizations. –TURNkey will not be a platform businesses can use to plan and coordinate with their critical business partners. Maybe in the future.

5.1.2 The revised TURNkey model

Figure 11 shows the developing TURNkey platform prototype as it was in May 2020. As a result of the last evaluation / critical review step conducted in February 2021 for PAR Cycle 1, this has been further refined. Figure 12 below, shows the latest version of the model based on the revised use cases mapped against the OEF/EEW/RRE timeline.

Figure 11 The TURNkey proposition (May 2020)

Figure 12 Revised use cases mapped against OEF/EEW/RRE timeline (Mar 2021)

6 NEXT STEPS – PAR CYCLE 2

The outputs from PAR Cycle 1, described in this report, will inform PAR Cycle 2. The aim of the PAR Cycle 2 is to present the second conceptual model and iteration of technical tools to end-user stakeholders and to test the user interface of the TURNkey system. Due to the travel restrictions imposed as a result of the current COVID pandemic, the PAR Cycle 2 will be conducted online. PAR Cycle 2 will consist of virtual workshops with end-user stakeholders using digital media. A virtual demonstrator has been developed to show the application of the TURNkey platform for typical earthquake scenarios. It shows end-users how the platform can be used for OEF, EEW and RRE. The demonstrator is intended as a research tool for facilitating both technical and operational discussions, to elicit scientific and operational feedback from potential users of the platform across the TBs. The virtual demonstrator will use a combination of graphics/data (which together provide information) from the emerging TURNkey user interface to test end-users understanding of the information presented and of its usefulness in decision-making for disaster risk reduction and improved earthquake resilience. The results from the testing of the second conceptual model, technical tools and user interface will be fed back to WP3, WP4 and WP5 through a series of virtual workshops. Reflection on the results from the PAR Cycle 2 will form a substantive part of the second consortium meeting. The results of the PAR Cycle 2 will be presented in deliverable D2.8 (revised use-cases for the FWCR platform version 2.0). This will in turn guide the development of the FWCR platform through PAR Cycle 3.

7 REFERENCES

- Adelman, C. (1993). Kurt Lewin and the origins of action research. *Educational action research*, 1(1), 7-24.
- Brandt, E. (2004). Action research in user-centred product development. *AI & SOCIETY*, 18(2), 113-133.
- Corporate Planning Unit, Gov. of St Lucia (2016) *Research Action Guide* Available on line at: www.govt.lc/media.govt.lc/www/resources/publications/action-research-booklet.pdf Accessed 29.03.21
- Coughlan, P., & Coughlan, D. (2002). Action research for operations management. *International journal of operations & production management*.
- Ferrario, M. A., Simm, W., Newman, P., Forshaw, S., & Whittle, J. (2014, May). Software engineering for social good': integrating action research, participatory design, and agile development. In *Companion Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Software Engineering* (pp. 520-523).
- Freire, P. (1996). *Pedagogy of the oppressed* (revised). New York: Continuum.
- Ghaffarian, V. (2011). The new stream of socio-technical approach and main stream information systems research. *Procedia Computer Science*, 3, 1499-1511.
- Interaction Design Foundation (2021) *Design iteration brings powerful results. So, do it again designer!* Available online at: www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/design-iteration-brings-powerful-results-so-do-it-again-designer Accessed 29.03.21
- Lau, F. (1997). A review on the use of action research in information systems studies. In *Information systems and qualitative research* (pp. 31-68). Springer, Boston, MA.
- Lewin, K. (1946). Action research and minority problems. *Journal of social issues*, 2(4), 34-46.
- Meyer, J. (2000). Using qualitative methods in health related action research. *Bmj*, 320(7228), 178-181.
- Ogata, Y. 1998. Space-time point-process models for earthquake occurrences, *Annals of the Institute of Statistical Mathematics*, 50, 379-402.
- Reason, P., & Bradbury, H. (Eds.). (2001). *Handbook of action research: Participative inquiry and practice*. Sage.
- Satriano, C., Elia, L., Martino, C., Lancieri, M., Zollo, A., & Iannaccone, G. (2011). PRESTo, the earthquake early warning system for southern Italy: Concepts, capabilities and future perspectives. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 31(2), 137-153.
- Smith, M. K. (1996; 2001, 2007, 2017) What is action research and how do we do it?, *The encyclopedia of pedagogy and informal education*. <https://infed.org/mobi/action-research/> Accessed 9th December 2020
- Tripp, D. (2005). Action research: a methodological introduction. *Educacao e pesquisa*, 31(3), 443-466.
- De Villiers, M. R. (2005, July). Three approaches as pillars for interpretive information systems research: development research, action research and grounded theory. In *Proceedings of the 2005 annual research conference of the South African institute of computer scientists and information technologists on IT research in developing countries* (pp. 142-151).

8 APPENDIX A – REVISED USE CASES

This appendix presents the revised use cases (UC). The original use cases were first published in TURNkey deliverable 1.3 (section 5) and 1.4 (sections 5 and 6). Changes to the original use cases have been marked in red.

8.1 EEW and RRE Use Cases Civil protection, first responders and citizens

8.1.1 UC: capturing and integrating multiple sources of information meaningfully and effectively

AMENDED: Whilst it is technically feasible to drill down for detail on a specific area, element of infrastructure or critical building, this is case dependent and requires satellite structural health monitoring. It could be done in advance at the level of the neighbourhood – but not for every single building. This feature will not be realized before the end of the project (see Table 10).

Table 13 UC: capturing and integrating multiple sources of information meaningfully and effectively

Goal:	To cut down on time and effort currently used to collate and process multiple and fragmentary data inputs
Use Case Instance:	To achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will assimilate incoming data from multiple sources such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • national and international seismic institutes • local infrastructure and road networks • critical buildings • reconnaissance and technical teams • rescue and other first responder teams <p>The platform will collate, categorize and present the information in such a way that facilitates a rapid understanding of current situation as well a reliable ranking of intervention priorities, along present criteria. The main TURNkey feature involved here will be the ‘earthquake cockpit situation report (detailed).</p>
Primary Actor:	End user at stakeholder organization receiving and processing incoming information
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End user at stakeholder organization whose responsibility is to monitor and relay accurate and relevant information • Stakeholder decision-maker who is responsible for determining priorities and allocating resources
Success guarantee:	Incoming data from: local, national and international sources, as well as locally-placed sensors data is organized, certified correct and presented in a user-friendly format allowing the user to quickly identify priority areas for intervention
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and stakeholders are starting to receive information and updates from seismic institutes as well as local reconnaissance teams

Success scenario:

- 1) First ground shaking alert received.
- 2) TURNkey platform rapidly 'populates' with information which is continuously updated. ~~This information can be further queried by 'drilling down' for detail on a specific area, element of infrastructure or critical building~~
- 3) Stakeholder user relays relevant information to decision-makers within their organization and other institutional users as necessary
- 4) Decision-makers are able to prioritize and allocate resources accordingly.

8.1.2 UC: faster response and mobilisation across multiple organisations

NO CHANGE

Table 14 UC: faster response and mobilisation across multiple organisations

Goal:	To cut down on time and resources required to effectively communicate and update other actors involved in rapid response phase
Use Case Instance:	<p>To achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will use previously input information to identify and contact third-party organizations and key personnel to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobilize local actors • Keep local organizations updated on the situation and/or protocols that may impact them <p>TURNkey features involved here are the: ‘automatic notifications’ and ‘call to action’ linked with ‘registry management’ will be used to make send rapid and automatic alerts to key players with minimal to no use of stakeholder resources</p>
Primary Actor:	End user at stakeholder organization responsible for alerting key actors
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End user at stakeholder organization whose responsibility is to identify and alert/call to action third party organizations or key decision makers • External organizations and decision-makers who have response protocols in place and who depend on alerts to set these in motion as well as maintain or termination actions
Success guarantee:	Automated, real-time alerts sent to targeted contact points communicating clear, concise, call-to-action message
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and stakeholders are mobilizing resources and activating protocols involving multiple organizations/local actors
Success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) First response stakeholder alerted and mobilized 2) TURNkey platform sends automated alert messages to pre-set third party contact points (or substitutes when these are not available) 3) Third-party contact points mobilize their own organizations/protocols in response in real-time.

8.1.3 UC: improved monitoring of first responders' wellbeing in the field

~~Improved visibility of danger to first responders in the field~~

AMENDED: it is scientifically not yet possible to alert first responders on the ground of incoming aftershocks (see Table 9).

Table 15 UC: improved monitoring of first responders' wellbeing in the field

Goal:	To safeguard first responders' wellbeing in the field through improved monitoring and two-way communication To safeguard first responders lives by alerting them to dangerous conditions on the ground
Use Case Instance:	Via a special first responder app, the TURNkey Platform will act as a two-way channel to communicate following information between central first responder headquarters and rescuers in the field: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> impacted buildings damage assessment other infrastructure infrastructure functionality / useability incoming aftershocks safe areas identification rescuer wellbeing status
Primary Actor:	First responder carrying out rescue operations
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First responders carrying out rescue operations are able to assess degree of danger before accessing collapsed structures and/or leave the building if an aftershock is anticipated First responder decision makers can communicate instructions aimed at safeguarding rescuers' lives via an app and monitor their wellbeing during rescue operations
Success guarantee:	Rapid alerts to signal a change in danger levels on site or to a rescuer's wellbeing Effective and timely two-way communication between HQ and field, as facilitated by the first responder app
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and first responder teams are in the field commencing rescue operations
Success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) An earthquake has occurred 2) Rescue teams have been mobilized 3) Central first responder site monitors danger levels at rescue site based on risk of collapse of buildings and/or incoming aftershocks 4) Central site maintains communications channel keeping on-site team informed if danger levels change so as to enable them to take preventative action 5) Central site also monitors individual rescuer wellbeing and alerts other rescuers on site should an intervention be required

8.1.4 UC: better communication and co-ordination of efforts across all institutions involved in the response phase

AMENDED: Whilst feasible from a scientific/engineering perspective, it is not part of TURNkey's focus to show the evolution of the rescue operation or support prioritisation exercises (see Table 11).

Table 16 UC: better communication and co-ordination of efforts across all institutions involved in the response phase

Goal:	To improve the co-ordination and effective intervention across all organizations mobilized after an earthquake
Use Case Instance:	<p>The TURNkey Platform will act as a central reference point for updates on the situation immediately after an earthquake. All users will be able to input and get access to updated information on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • location and extent of damages, affected areas and infrastructure viability • Intervention sites and progress on same • Ongoing prioritization exercises <p>The main TURNkey feature involved here is the 'earthquake cockpit situation report' and 'evolution of rescue operation' 'with additional input from 'eye witness observation', 'damage assessment' and safe areas identification'.</p>
Primary Actor:	External institutions involved in the response phase
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First responders needing to maintain communication and co-ordinate efforts with external organizations • External organizations activating response protocols and/or needing to work with first responders in the immediate response phase
Success guarantee:	All actors are fully aware of how the situation is progressing enabling swift and appropriate action avoiding redundancy and/or conflicting action
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and the first response is underway. All external organizations have been alerted to the situation.
Success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) An earthquake has occurred 2) First responders have been mobilized 3) External organizations have been alerted 4) External organizations launch their respective response protocols and monitor the situation on the TURNkey platform responding to changes or instructions carried there accordingly

8.1.5 UC: a smart operating system that collates state of infrastructure for the planning of rescue operations

NO CHANGE

Table 17 UC: a smart operating system that collates state of infrastructure for the planning of rescue operations

Goal:	To capture an up-to-date snapshot of which elements of local infrastructure are hit/operational
Use Case Instance:	The TURNkey Platform will receive continuously updated information from various sources to give: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • location and extent of damages to buildings, strategic infrastructure and road networks • number and location of infrastructure units still operational. <p>The main TURNkey features involved here are: infrastructure management, with lower interest in ‘damage assessment’ and ‘eyewitness observation’.</p>
Primary Actor:	All institutions involved in planning rescue operations
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First responder decision-makers planning travel and launch of rescue operations on affected sites • External organizations activating response protocols and/or needing to work with first responders in the immediate response phase
Success guarantee:	All actors are fully aware of viable routes and other key infrastructure involved in bringing injured citizens to required medical attention (e.g. hospitals)
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and the first response is underway. All rescue organizations have been alerted to the situation.
Success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) An earthquake has occurred 2) First responder organizations have been alerted 3) Other rescue organizations have been alerted 4) First responders and other rescue organizations plan travel to affected site and rescue operations including nearest operational medical infrastructure

8.2 EEW Use Cases Critical Infrastructure and General Business

8.2.1 Improved safety use-cases

8.2.1.1 UC: personal safety of employees working at height

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems (such as personal alerts) will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

It is not technically feasible for TURNkey to issue an 'all clear' after ground shaking has stopped.

Table 18 UC: personal safety of employees working at height

Goal:	To reduce the risk of falling from height due to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	To achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert any employee working at height will check their personal safety equipment (safety lines and harnesses) and then mentally and physically prepare themselves for ground shaking (preferred safe action), or if sufficient time warning can be given, move to a safer location (secondary safe action) if their current location is perceived to be very high risk. Once ground shaking ceases the employee will return to the ground and evacuate the building. The employee will not return to working at this location until full post-earthquake inspections have been complete and the area is deemed safe.
Primary Actor:	The employee working at height.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The employee who needs a timely alert; • The employee's manager who wants to know that an alert has been issued and received; • The organisations health and safety manager who needs to know how many employees working at height have been received the alert and where they are working; • The TURNkey system who wants to issue true-positive alerts.
Success guarantee:	Employee does not fall as a consequence of ground shaking. Or the employee has time to return to the ground before ground shaking starts.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow employees to check their safety lines and harnesses and confirm that they are correctly attached.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received 2) The business organisations' employee personal alert system is activated [FUTURE]. 3) Employee checks safety lines and harnesses and confirms that they are correctly attached. 4) employee braces themselves for ground shaking. 5) when ground shaking stops and TURNkey management issues the 'all clear', the employee detaches safety equipment and returns to the ground. Employee evacuates the area and reports to their manager.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) Employee checks safety lines and harnesses and confirms that they are correctly attached. 3) Employee braces themselves for ground shaking, but no ground shaking occurs. 3) Employee awaits the "all clear" 4) Employee either continues working or returns to the ground and seeks further advice. 5) Employee loses confidence in the system.

Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs (false-negative alert). 3) Employee falls. 4) Employee loses confidence in the system.
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8.2.1.2 UC: personal safety of employers working in confined spaces

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems (such as personal alerts) will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

It is not technically feasible for TURNkey to issue an ‘all clear’ after ground shaking has stopped.

Table 19 UC: personal safety of employers working in confined spaces – instance 1: working in a tunnel

Goal:	To reduce the risk of being trapped in confined spaces due to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 1 (working in a tunnel): To achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert any employee working in a tunnel will make their way to the exit point and leave the tunnel. Once they have exited the tunnel the employee will inform their manager of their situation. The employee will not return to working in the tunnel until full post-earthquake inspections have been complete and the area is deemed safe.
Primary Actor:	The employee working in a tunnel.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The employee who needs a timely alert; • The employee’s manager who wants to know that an alert has been issued and received; • The organisations health and safety manager who needs to know how many employees working in tunnels have received the alert and where they are located; • The TURNkey system who wants to issue true-positive alerts.
Success guarantee:	Employee is able to vacate the tunnel before ground shaking starts.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow employees to make their way to the tunnel exit point and exit the tunnel before ground shaking starts
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The business organisations’ employee personal alert system is activated [FUTURE]. 2) Employee makes their way to the tunnel exit point and exit the tunnel before ground shaking starts. 3) When ground shaking stops and TURNkey management issues the ‘all clear’, employee evacuates the area and reports to their manager.

Alternate scenario – True-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) TURNkey platform issues an alert but this is not received by the employee due to the physical constraints of the tunnel working environment (e.g., the signal fails to penetrate the tunnel infrastructure). 2) Ground shaking starts and the employee is trapped in the tunnel. 3) Employee loses confidence in the system.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. Employee makes their way to the tunnel exit point and exits the tunnel, but no ground shaking occurs. 2) Employee awaits the “all clear”. 3) Employee either continues working or seeks further advice. 4) Employee loses confidence in the system
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs and the employee is trapped in the tunnel. 3) Employee loses confidence in the system.

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems (such as personal alerts) will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

It is not technically feasible for TURNkey to issue an ‘all clear’ after ground shaking has stopped.

Table 20 personal safety of employers working in confined spaces – instance 2: working in a crawl space

Goal:	To reduce the risk of being trapped in confined spaces due to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 2 (working in a crawl space under heavy equipment/machinery): To achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert any employee working in a crawl space will make their way to the exit point and leave the crawl space. Once they have exited the crawl space the employee will inform their manager of their situation. The employee will not return to working in the crawl space until full post-earthquake inspections have been complete and the area is deemed safe.
Primary Actor:	The employee working in a crawl space.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The employee who needs a timely alert; • The employee’s manager who wants to know that an alert has been issued and received; • The organisations health and safety manager who needs to know how many employees working in crawl spaces have received the alert and where they are located; • The TURNkey system who wants to issue true-positive alerts.
Success guarantee:	Employee is able to vacate the crawl space before ground shaking starts.

Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow employees to make their way to the crawl space exit point and exit the crawl space before ground shaking starts.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The business organisations' employee personal alert system is activated [FUTURE]. 3) Employee makes their way to the crawl space exit point and exits the crawl space before ground shaking starts. 4) When ground shaking stops and TURNkey management issues the 'all clear', employee evacuates the area and reports to their manager.
Alternate scenario – True-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) TURNkey platform issues an alert but this is not received by the employee due to the physical constraints of the crawl space environment (e.g., the signal is missed because of other circumstances-for example loud noises masking an audible alert alarm). 2) Ground shaking starts and the employee is trapped in the in the crawl space. 3) Employee loses confidence in the system.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) Employee makes their way to the crawl space exit point and exits the crawl space, but no ground shaking occurs. 3) Employee awaits the “all clear”. 4) Employee either continues working or seeks further advice. 5) Employee loses confidence in the system.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs and the employee is trapped in the crawl space. 3) Employee loses confidence in the system.

8.2.1.3 UC: safety to employees from falling objects

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems (such as personal alerts) will not be realized before the end of the TURNKEY project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

It is not technically feasible for TURNkey to issue an ‘all clear’ after ground shaking has stopped.

Table 21 UC: safety to employees from falling objects - instance 1: employees working at height

Goal:	To reduce the risk of objects falling from height due to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 1 (temporary equipment being used by employees working at height): To achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert any employee working at height will check that any equipment they are using is firmly secured by safety lines (which should be normal working practice). Also, the employee who is responsible for maintaining an exclusion zone below anybody working at height (which should be normal working practice) will

	ensure that nobody is in the exclusion zone. Once ground shaking ceases the employee will return all temporary equipment to the ground and ensure it is stored in a safe manner, including returning equipment to central storage if necessary (in the case of specialist storage requirements being necessary - e.g., to minimise chemical spillage).
Primary Actor:	The employee working at height and their ground level support colleagues.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The employees who needs a timely alert; • The employee's manager who wants to know that an alert has been issued and received; • The organisations health and safety manager who needs to know how many employees working at height have received the alert and where they are working; • The TURNkey system who wants to issue true-positive alerts.
Success guarantee:	Temporary equipment does not fall as a consequence of ground shaking. Or if equipment does for it lands in the exclusion zone which is clear of other employees.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow employees to check safety lines of equipment and ensure that the exclusion zone is clear of other employees.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The business organisations' employee personal alert system is activated [FUTURE]. 2) Employees check safety lines of equipment and ensures that the exclusion zone is clear of other employees. 3) When ground shaking stops and TURNkey management issues the 'all clear', employee detaches equipment safety lines and returns the equipment to the ground where it is safely stored. 4) Employee evacuates the area and reports to their manager.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) Employee checks safety lines of equipment and ensures that the exclusion zone is clear of other employees, but no ground shaking occurs. 3) Employee awaits the "all clear". 4) Employee either continues working or seeks further advice. 5) Employee loses confidence in the system.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) Temporary equipment falls and injures people below. 4) Employee and the business lose confidence in the system.

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems (such as personal alerts) will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

It is not technically feasible for TURNkey to issue an 'all clear' after ground shaking has stopped.

Table 22 UC: safety to employees from falling objects - instance 2: crane/forklift truck operations

Goal:	To reduce the risk of objects falling from height due to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 2 (objects falling during the process of being lifted into place - e.g., crane/forklift truck operations): to achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert any employee operating equipment that is lifting/lowering objects to/from height (e.g., warehouse storage, loading unloading vehicles, transporting products using overhead cranes etc) will immediately return the objects to a safe location on the ground or to their original stored position if this is the safer option. The employee operating the lifting equipment will follow their evacuation protocols for earthquakes (which could be to stay in place if this is the safest option). Once ground shaking ceases the employee will not recommence lifting activities until full post-earthquake inspections have been complete.
Primary Actor:	The employee operating lifting equipment.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The employees who needs a timely alert; • The employee's manager who wants to know that an alert has been issued and received; • The organisations health and safety manager who needs to know how many employees involved in lifting activities have received the alert and where they are working; • The TURNkey system who wants to issue true-positive alerts.
Success guarantee:	Lifting activities cease and objects being lifted are either returned to the ground (preferred solution) or their original location (alternate solution).
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow employees operating lifting equipment to assess their fail-safe actions.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The business organisations' employee personal alert system is activated [FUTURE]. 2) Employees operating lifting equipment assess their fail-safe actions (immediate return to ground or original location) and initiate the most appropriate action. 3) Once the object is in its fail-safe location, ground shaking stops and TURNkey management issues the 'all clear' the employee follows the earthquake evacuation protocol and reports to their manager.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) Employees operating lifting equipment assess their fail-safe actions (immediate return to ground or original location) and initiate the most appropriate action, but no ground shaking occurs. 3) Employee awaits the “all clear”. 4) Employee either continues working or seeks further advice. 5) Employee loses confidence in the system.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs.

	<p>3) Objects fall whilst being lifted and injures people below.</p> <p>4) Employee and the business lose confidence in the system.</p>
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8.2.1.4 UC: community safety from toxic substances

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

Table 23 UC: community safety from toxic substances

Goal:	To reduce the risk to the local community of toxic substance spillage due to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	(Gaseous or liquid chemical leak): To achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert automated systems within the business organisation will activate procedures to isolate critical assets and minimise (ideally to zero) gaseous chemical leaks following an earthquake (note: storage and transmission assets have been designed to earthquake standards and have detailed risk assessment/management protocols in place to deal with this potential scenario). Critical assets will remain isolated until post-earthquake inspections have taken place in the critical assets are deemed safe to return to normal operating mode. Note: this use case instance is based upon a hypothetical situation that would have existed at one of the Testbeds before the production procedure was changed to remove reliance upon toxicity chemicals.
Primary Actor:	The organisations automated control system.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The automated control system that needs a timely alert; • The business organisations senior management who want to know that an alert has been issued and received, and that the automated fail-safe protocols have been successfully activated; • The organisations health and safety manager who needs to know that the critical systems have been put into fail-safe mode; • The TURNkey system who wants to issue true-positive alerts.
Success guarantee:	The critical asset is placed in its fail-safe mode and no gaseous chemical leak results from ground shaking.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow the critical asset to achieve its fail-safe mode.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The business organisations automated control systems are activated [FUTURE]. 3) The business organisations automated control systems report to senior management when fail-safe mode is achieved [FUTURE]. 4) No gaseous or liquid chemical leak occurs.
Alternate scenario – True-Positive alert	1) TURNkey platform issues an alert but this does not provide sufficient time for the critical asset to achieve its fail-safe mode.

	<p>2) Ground shaking starts and the critical asset is damaged resulting in a gaseous chemical release.</p> <p>3) The business organisation and local community loses confidence in the system.</p>
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<p>1) Ground shaking alert received.</p> <p>2) The critical asset is placed into fail-safe mode, but no ground shaking occurs.</p> <p>3) The production process that relies on the normal operation of the critical asset is stopped.</p> <p>4) Business losses are incurred (e.g., due to waste of partially finished products, due to long lead-in times to restart the critical asset, etc)</p>
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<p>1) No alert is received.</p> <p>2) Ground shaking occurs and there is a gaseous chemical release.</p> <p>3) Business organisation and the community loses confidence in the system.</p>

8.2.1.5 UC: safety of high-speed trains

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

Table 24 UC: safety of high-speed trains – instance 1: derailment on open air track

Goal:	To avoid derailment of a high-speed train with consequent damage to people (passengers and staff)
Use Case Instance:	Instance 1 (derailment on open air track): to achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert automated systems within the business organisation will trigger an alert in the driver’s cab that will apply the brake and an automatic control on the energy supply to reduce the speed. After the earthquake the train is evacuated and passengers transported through buses. The rail track is not used until automatic and eventually manual check is carried out.
Primary Actor:	The train operator company and eventually the train driver.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The train operator company; • The rail track owner company; • Insurance company. • Reduce payment for morbidity and mortality; • Reduce further damage to train and rail track.
Success guarantee:	Train does not derail and people are not injured or die.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow the critical asset to slow down the speed until stopping the train.
Main success scenario:	<p>1) Ground shaking alert received.</p> <p>2) The train operator’s automated alarm for driver and automated control system for train power supply are activated [FUTURE]</p>

	<p>3) Train slows down the speed and stop.</p> <p>4) Rescue team is sent to rescue passengers and staff.</p>
Alternate scenario – True-Positive alert	<p>1) TURNkey platform issues an alert but this does not provide sufficient time for the critical asset to slow down the speed until stopping the train.</p> <p>2) Ground shaking reaches the rail track when the train has only partially reduced the speed.</p> <p>3) Reduced possibility of derailment or derailment at lower speed causes less damages.</p> <p>4) Damages to passengers and staff are paid.</p>
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<p>1) Ground shaking alert received.</p> <p>2) No ground shaking occurs.</p> <p>3) The train stops.</p> <p>4) Rescue team is sent to rescue passengers and staff.</p> <p>5) Rail track are checked.</p> <p>6) Train operator or insurance paid delay.</p>
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<p>1) No alert is received.</p> <p>2) Ground shaking occurs and train derails.</p> <p>3) Passenger and staff are injured or die.</p> <p>4) Train operator or insurance pay the damages.</p> <p>5) Loss of clients due to reduced confidence of passengers on the service provided.</p>

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

Table 25 UC: safety of high-speed trains – instance 2: derailment in tunnel

Goal:	To avoid derailment of a high-speed train with consequent damage to people (passengers and staff)
Use Case Instance:	Instance 2 (derailment in tunnel): to achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert automated systems within the business organisation will trigger an alert in the driver's cab that will apply the brake and an automatic control on the energy supply to reduce the speed. If the train must still enter the tunnel, light is turned to red. After the earthquake the train is evacuated (through the auxiliary tunnel before and then passengers and staff transported through buses. The rail track is not used until automatic and eventually manual check is carried out.
Primary Actor:	The train operator company and eventually the train driver.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The train operator company; the rail track owner company; • Insurance company. • Reduce payment for morbidity and mortality • Reduce further damage to train and rail track.
Success guarantee:	Train does not derail and people are not injured or die.

Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow the critical asset to slow down the speed until stopping the train
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The train operator's automated alarm for driver and automated control system for energy supply are activated [FUTURE] 3) Train slows down the speed and stop. 4) Rescue team is sent to rescue passengers and staff.
Alternate scenario – True-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) TURNkey platform issues an alert but this does not provide sufficient time for the critical asset to slow down the speed until stopping the train. 2) Ground shaking reaches the rail track when the train has only partially reduced the speed. 3) Reduced possibility of derail or derail at lower speed causes less damages. 4) Damages to passengers and staff are paid.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) The train stops. 4) Rescue team is sent to rescue passengers and staff. 5) Rail track are checked. 6) Train operator or insurance paid delay.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs and train derails. 3) Passengers and staff are injured or die. 4) Train operator or insurance pay the damages. 5) Loss of clients due to reduced confidence of passengers on the service provided.

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

Table 26 UC: safety of high-speed trains – instance 3: derailment on bridge

Goal:	To avoid derailment of a high-speed train with consequent damage to people (passengers and staff)
Use Case Instance:	Instance 3 (derailment on bridge): to achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert automated systems within the business organisation will trigger an alert in the driver's cab that will apply the brake and an automatic control on the energy supply to reduce the speed. If the train must still cross the abutment, light is turned to red. After the earthquake the train is evacuated (through the auxiliary tunnel before and then passengers and staff transported through buses. The rail track is not used until automatic and eventually manual check is carried out.
Primary Actor:	The train operator company and eventually the train driver.

Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The train operator company; • The rail track owner company; • Insurance company. • Reduce payment for morbidity and mortality; • Reduce further damage to train and rail track.
Success guarantee:	Train does not derail and people are not injured or die.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow the critical asset to slow down the speed until stopping the train.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The train operator's automated alarm for driver and automated control system for train power supply are activated [FUTURE] 3) Train slows down the speed and stop. 4) Rescue team is sent to rescue passengers and staff.
Alternate scenario – True-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) TURNkey platform issues an alert but this does not provide sufficient time for the critical asset to slow down the speed until stopping the train 2) Ground shaking reaches the rail track when the train has only partially reduced the speed. 3) Reduced possibility of derail or derail without falling from the bridge. 4) Damages to passengers and staff are paid.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) The train stops. 4) Rescue team is sent to rescue passengers and staff. 5) Rail track are checked. 6) Train operator or insurance paid delay.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs and train derails. 3) Passengers and staff are injured or die. 4) Train operator or insurance pay the damages. 5) Loss of clients due to reduced confidence of passengers on the service provided.

8.2.1.6 UC: safety of gas distribution networks

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

Table 27 UC: safety of gas distribution networks

Goal:	To avoid gas leakage and consequent explosions.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 1 (high and medium pressure gas pipeline): To achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert the gas distribution company seismic risk team

	decides eventually to close medium or high-pressure gas pipelines. After the earthquake if no damage is detected in the pipeline they are reopened.
Primary Actor:	The gas distribution company and its seismic risk team.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The gas distribution company. • Reduce damages due to consequent explosions to third parties.
Success guarantee:	No triggered explosion.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow for the safe automatic turn off of medium and high-pressure gas pipelines [FUTURE] .
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) Seismic risk assessor team of the gas company turn off the automatic valves of medium and high-pressure gas pipeline. 3) No gaseous leakage or explosion occurs
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) Seismic risk assessor team of the gas company turn off the automatic valves of medium and high-pressure gas pipeline. 5) Gas pipelines are checked. 6) Company incurs financial loss due to downtime 6) Company loses confidence in the system
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs followed by gas leakage and a consequent explosion. 3) Staff or citizens are injured or die. 4) Gas company or insurance pay the damages. 5) Company loses confidence in the system.

8.2.2 Improved business operation use-cases - post-earthquake recovery

8.2.2.1 UC: minimise direct damage to critical system

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

Table 28 UC: minimise direct damage to critical system – instance 1: damage to production systems, autonomous control

Goal:	To reduce potential damage to critical business systems as a result of ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 1 (damage to production systems caused by ground shaking - autonomous control): To achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert autonomous systems would be activated to either stop the production process partway through (either immediately or at the next process step fail-safe mode) and evacuate the building. Once ground shaking ceases the

	production process will be reset (it is likely to require additional work to reconfigure the production process before it can be restarted) and restarted once full post-earthquake inspections have been complete and the area is deemed safe.
Primary Actor:	The production processes autonomous control systems.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The production process autonomous control system which needs a timely alert; • The production manager who needs to be aware that the safe-shutdown process has been initiated in response to an EEW alert; • The organisations senior production manager who needs to be aware of the impact of the shutdown on upstream and downstream logistics; • The TURNkey system who wants to issue true-positive alerts.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow safe-shutdown to be achieved (note: this will be production process dependent).
Success guarantee:	The production process is stopped in a safe-mode and is not significantly damaged as a consequence of ground shaking starts.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The production process autonomous system initiates a safe stopping of the production process [FUTURE]. 3) When ground shaking stops there is minimal damage to the production process. 4) The production process can be restarted reasonably quickly after ground shaking stops.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) The production process is stopped in a safe-mode. 4) The production process needs to be reset before it can be restarted. 5) The production processes restarted but the business organisation has incurred financial loss.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) The production process is damaged during ground shaking. 4) The business organisation incurs financial loss. 5) The business loses confidence in the system.

NO CHANGE

Table 29 UC: minimise direct damage to critical system – instance 2: damage to production systems, manual control

Goal:	To reduce potential damage to critical business systems as a result of ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 2 (damage to production systems caused by ground shaking - manual control): to achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert manual

	operatives would either stop the production process partway through (either immediately or at the next process step fail-safe mode) and evacuate the building. Once ground shaking ceases the production process will be reset (it is likely to require additional work to reconfigure the production process before it can be restarted) and restarted once full post-earthquake inspections have been complete and the area is deemed safe.
Primary Actor:	The production processes manual control systems.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The production process manual (human) control system which needs a timely alert. • The production manager who needs to be aware that the safe-shutdown process has been initiated in response to an EEW alert. • The organisations senior production manager who needs to be aware of the impact of the shutdown on upstream and downstream logistic. • The TURNkey system who wants to issue true-positive alerts.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow safe-shutdown to be achieved (note: this will be production process dependent).
Success guarantee:	The production process is stopped in a safe-mode and is not significantly damaged as a consequence of ground shaking starts.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The production process manual system initiates a safe stopping of the production process. 3) When ground shaking stops there is minimal damage to the production process. 4) The production process can be restarted reasonably quickly after ground shaking stops.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) The production process is stopped in a safe-mode. 4) The production process needs to be reset before it can be restarted. 5) The production processes restarted but the business organisation has incurred financial loss.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) The production process is damaged during ground shaking. 4) The business organisation incurs financial loss. 5) The business loses confidence in the system.

FUTURE – Ways to facilitate the optional integration of TURNkey EEW alerts with automated in-house business systems will not be realized before the end of the TURNKey project. However, there are no technical barriers to overcome. As such, this use case may be actualised in the future.

Table 30 UC: minimise direct damage to critical system – instance 3: damage to support systems, autonomous control

Goal:	To reduce potential damage to critical business systems as a result of ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 3 (damage to support systems caused by ground shaking – autonomous control): to achieve this goal the TURNkey Platform will issue an alert when an earthquake is detected. On receipt of this alert autonomous systems would be activated to stop support systems (e.g., power supply, raw material supply etc) in a stop-safe mode to reduce damage to either the support system or the primary production process. Consideration would need to be given to the impact that stopping a support system would have on the production process, and in particular on the safe operation of the production process. As such, autonomous control of support systems would need to be designed as an integral part of the control of the production process. Once ground shaking ceases the support system will be reset (it is likely to require additional work to reconfigure the support system before it can be restarted) and restarted once full post-earthquake inspections have been complete and the area is deemed safe.
Primary Actor:	The support systems autonomous control system.
Stakeholders and Interests:	The systems autonomous control system which needs a timely alert; the production manager who needs to be aware that the safe-shutdown of the support system has been initiated in response to an EEW alert; the organisations senior production manager who needs to be aware of the impact of the shutdown on upstream and downstream logistics; the TURNkey system who wants to issue true-positive alerts.
Preconditions:	An earthquake has occurred and a specified time delay alert can be issued that is sufficient to allow safe-shutdown to be achieved (note: this will be support system dependent).
Success guarantee:	The support system is stopped in a safe-mode and is not significantly damaged as a consequence of ground shaking starts.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) The support systems autonomous system initiates a safe stopping mode [FUTURE]. 3) When ground shaking stops there is minimal damage to the support system. 4) The support system can be restarted reasonably quickly after ground shaking stops.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ground shaking alert received. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) The support system is stopped in a safe-mode. 4) The support system needs to be reset before it can be restarted (this is not likely to be a long task for most support systems - a matter of seconds or minutes). 5) the support system is restarted but the business organisation has incurred financial loss (due to impact on primary production processes).
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No alert is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) The support system is damaged during ground shaking. 4) The business organisation incurs financial loss.

	5) the business loses confidence in the system. 6) Staff evacuation.
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8.3 OEF Use Cases Critical Infrastructure and General Business

8.3.1 Improved employee safety

8.3.1.1 UC: personal safety of employees (rescheduling of work tasks)

TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., ‘red alert for the next 48 hours’). It is not technically feasible to give an end time. TURNkey will not provide OEF directly to critical infrastructure providers and businesses, but indirectly – via civil protection.

Table 31 UC: personal safety of employees (rescheduling of work tasks) – instance 1: non-time critical tasks

Goal:	To reduce the risk to employee safety due to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 1 (non-time critical tasks): To achieve this goal, the TURNkey Platform will issue OEF's of an increased likelihood of ground shaking over a pre-determined time period real time updates of changes in seismic hazard for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG system – red, amber, green). The OEF would be in the form of risk levels (green – no increased risk level, yellow, amber, red). TURNkey will notify critical infrastructure providers and general businesses of changes in risk to their assets. It will do so indirectly, via civil protection. The TURNkey risk levels would be considered by the business organisation against specific operational (and potentially business) risk scenarios and the specific risks to the business organisation would be identified. Depending upon the business organisations risk tolerance (note: it is likely that the same business organisation would have different risk tolerances for different business activities) non-time critical business activities (e.g., routine maintenance) that were considered ‘high’ risk would be rescheduled until the OEF had returned to green.
Primary Actor:	The business managers responsible for scheduling of work tasks.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The business manager; related business managers who may be affected by rescheduling of work (e.g., warehouse manager, production manager, logistics manager etc). The organisations health and safety manager who monitors risk levels; the TURNkey system who wants to issue reliable forecasts.
Success guarantee:	No employees are injured during ground shaking as a consequence of undertaking tasks that could have been delayed until the forecast level had returned to green.
Preconditions:	Real-time updates of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties, showing seismic hazard and risk to assets.

	An earthquake forecast (green, yellow, amber, red) has been issued with an associated timeframe (e.g., red forecast for the next 48 hours).
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) OEF received by the business organisation via civil protection (this could be push notification, pull notification or both). 2) Business managers responsible for scheduling non-time critical tasks review the forecasts at their daily meetings and either accelerate tasks so that they are completed before the forecast ground shaking starts or delay tasks until the forecast level returns to green. 3) Other managers who are affected by the change schedules ensure that their colleagues are aware of the circumstances and take appropriate management actions to minimise financial loss (e.g., adjust upstream and downstream logistic supply chains, including liaising with suppliers and specialist subcontractors etc).
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Red OEF issued. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) Business organisation incurs financial loss (although this was not considered to be a major concern for most interviewees - it was heavily outweighed by their sense of corporate social responsibility).
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No forecast is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) Employee suffer injury which could have been avoided if they had not been undertaking the specific activity. 4) Business organisation and employee lose confidence in the system.

TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., ‘red alert for the next 48 hours’). It is not technically feasible to give an end time. TURNkey will not provide OEF directly to critical infrastructure providers and businesses, but indirectly – via civil protection.

Table 32 UC: personal safety of employees (rescheduling of work tasks) – instance 2: time critical tasks

Goal:	To reduce the risk to employee safety due to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	<p>Instance 2 (time critical tasks): To achieve this goal, the TURNkey Platform will issue OEF's of an increased likelihood of ground shaking over a pre-determined time period real time updates of changes in seismic hazard for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG system – red, amber, green). The OEF would be in the form of risk levels (green—no increased risk level, yellow, amber, red). TURNkey will notify critical infrastructure providers and general businesses of changes in risk to their assets. It will do so indirectly, via civil protection. The TURNkey risk levels would be considered by the business organisation against specific operational (and potentially business) risk scenarios and the specific risks to the business organisation would be identified. Depending upon the business organisations risk tolerance (note: it is likely that the same business organisation would have different risk tolerances for different business</p>

	activities) time critical business activities (e.g., production activities) that were considered 'high' risk would be suspended until the OEF had returned to green. This suspension would be dependent upon the downtime estimate of the OEF being red (if the downtime required for the OEF to reduce to green was too great then the restart time could be too long to justify shutting the activity down).
Primary Actor:	The business managers responsible for time critical work tasks.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The business manager. • The general workforce who may be affected by changed shift patterns. • Related business managers who may be affected by rescheduling of work (e.g., warehouse manager, production manager, logistics manager etc). • The organisations health and safety manager who monitors risk levels. • The business organisation senior management. • The TURNkey system who wants to issue reliable forecasts.
Preconditions:	<p>Real time updates of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties, showing seismic hazard and risk to assets.</p> <p>An earthquake forecast (green, yellow, amber, red) has been issued with an associated timeframe (e.g., red forecast for the next 48 hours).</p>
Success guarantee:	No employees are injured during ground shaking as a consequence of undertaking tasks that could have been delayed until the forecast level had returned to green.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) OEF received by the business organisation via civil protection (this could be push notification, pull notification or both). 2) Business managers responsible for scheduling time critical tasks review the forecasts at their daily meetings and either accelerate tasks so that they are completed before the forecast ground shaking starts or delay tasks until the forecast level returns to green. 3) Other managers who are affected by the change schedules ensure that their colleagues are aware of the circumstances and take appropriate management actions to minimise financial loss (e.g., adjust upstream and downstream logistic supply chains, including liaising with suppliers and specialist subcontractors etc). 4) Senior managers who are responsible for assessing business risks consider the wider business implications (e.g., on customers etc) and accept these risks.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Red OEF issued. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) Business organisation incurs financial loss (these losses could be substantial if the business organisation fails to deliver its product/service to its customers in line with contractual agreements).

Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No forecast is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) Employee suffer injury which could have been avoided if they had not been undertaking the specific activity. 4) Business organisation and employee loses confidence in the system.
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8.3.1.2 UC: personal safety of employees (enhanced health and safety checks)

TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., ‘red alert for the next 48 hours’). It is not technically feasible to give an end time. TURNkey will not provide OEF directly to critical infrastructure providers and businesses, but indirectly – via civil protection.

Table 33 UC: personal safety of employees (enhanced health and safety checks)

Goal: To reduce the risk to employee safety due to ground shaking	
Use Case Instance:	<p>Instance (health and safety checks of critical areas):</p> <p>To achieve this goal, the TURNkey Platform will issue OEF's of an increased likelihood of ground shaking over a pre-determined time period real time updates of changes in seismic hazard for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG system – red, amber, green). The OEF would be in the form of risk levels (green – no increased risk level, yellow, amber, red). TURNkey will notify critical infrastructure providers and general businesses of changes in risk to their assets. It will do so indirectly, via civil protection. The TURNkey risk levels would be considered by the business organisation against specific operational (and potentially business) risk scenarios and the specific risks to the business organisation would be identified. Depending upon the business organisations risk tolerance (note: it is likely that the same business organisation would have different risk tolerances for different business activities) detailed inspections of all business areas will be performed by risk managers to ensure that all health and safety procedures and protocols were properly in place (e.g., checking that all non-permanent equipment was stored in a safe manner - ladders fastened back, that on-site medical facilities were fully stocked, that all evacuation routes were clear of obstacles etc).</p>
Primary Actor:	The risk managers responsible for health and safety.
Stakeholders and Interests:	The risk manager; related business managers who are responsible for specific areas within the business organisation; the organisations senior health and safety manager who monitors risk levels; the TURNkey system who wants to issue reliable forecasts.
Preconditions:	<p>Real time updates of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties, showing seismic hazard and risk to assets.</p> <p>An earthquake forecast (green, yellow, amber, red) has been issued with an associated timeframe (e.g., red forecast for the next 48 hours).</p>

Success guarantee:	No employees are injured during ground shaking as a consequence of lax health and safety controls.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) OEF received by the business organisation via civil protection (this could be push notification, pull notification or both). 2) Risk managers responsible review the forecasts at their daily meetings with operational managers and initiate formal health and safety checks across the business organisation. 3) Operational managers (or their delegated authorities) formally undertake & off risk assessments against the standard earthquake risk scenario.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Red OEF issued. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) business organisation incurs financial loss (although this was not considered to be a major concern for most interviewees - it was heavily outweighed by their sense of corporate social responsibility).
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No forecast is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) Employee suffer injury as a consequence of lax health and safety controls. 4) Business organisation and employee lose confidence in the system.

8.3.1.3 UC: personal safety of employees (safe warehousing)

TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., ‘red alert for the next 48 hours’). It is not technically feasible to give an end time. TURNkey will not provide OEF directly to critical infrastructure providers and businesses, but indirectly – via civil protection.

Table 34 UC: personal safety of employees (safe warehousing)

Goal: To reduce the risk to employee safety due to ground shaking	
Use Case Instance:	<p>Use Case Instance (safe warehousing):</p> <p>To achieve this goal, the TURNkey Platform will issue OEF's of an increased likelihood of ground shaking over a pre-determined time period real time updates of changes in seismic hazard for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG system – red, amber, green). The OEF would be in the form of risk levels (green – no increased risk level, yellow, amber, red). TURNkey will notify critical infrastructure providers and general businesses of changes in risk to their assets. It will do so indirectly, via civil protection. The TURNkey risk levels would be considered by the business organisation against specific operational (and potentially business) risk scenarios and the specific risks to the business organisation would be identified. Depending upon the business organisations risk tolerance (note: it is likely that the same business organisation would have different risk tolerances for different business activities) warehoused supplies would be temporarily relocated to low-risk storage areas (e.g., ground level including outside).</p>

Primary Actor:	The warehouse manager.
Stakeholders and Interests:	The risk manager; related business managers who are responsible for specific areas within the business organisation; the organisations senior health and safety manager who monitors risk levels; the TURNkey system who wants to issue reliable forecasts.
Preconditions:	Real time updates of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties, showing seismic hazard and risk to assets. An earthquake forecast (green, yellow, amber, red) has been issued with an associated timeframe (e.g., red forecast for the next 48 hours).
Success guarantee:	No employees are injured during ground shaking as a consequence of items falling from storage areas.
Main success scenario:	1) OEF received by the business organisation via civil protection (this could be push notification, pull notification or both). 2) Logistic manager initiates a re-storage protocol to move objects from shelving to ground level to reduce the loss of injury to warehouse employees, or damage to warehouse stock items that could be needed to repair business critical systems after ground shaking. 3) Logistics manager communicates with external suppliers to reschedule delivery of supplies (either accelerate or delay supply until forecast level returns to green).
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	1) Red OEF issued. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) Business organisation incurs financial loss (although this was not considered to be a major concern for most interviewees - it was heavily outweighed by their sense of corporate social responsibility).
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	1) No forecast is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) Employee suffer injury as a consequence of falling items. 4) Business organisation recovery is delayed because of damage to critical repair items. 5) Business organisation and employee loses confidence in the system.

8.3.2 Reduction to business disruption

8.3.2.1 UC: Repair Teams on Standby

TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., ‘red alert for the next 48 hours’). It is not technically feasible to give an end time. TURNkey will not provide OEF directly to critical infrastructure providers and businesses, but indirectly – via civil protection.

Table 35 UC: Repair Teams on Standby

Goal:	To ensure that critical members of repair teams are available to initiate repairs.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 1 (Standby Teams):

	<p>To achieve this goal, the TURNkey Platform will issue OEF's of an increased likelihood of ground shaking over a pre-determined time period real time updates of changes in seismic hazard for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG system – red, amber, green). The OEF would be in the form of risk levels (green – no increased risk level, yellow, amber, red). TURNkey will notify critical infrastructure providers and general businesses of changes in risk to their assets. It will do so indirectly, via civil protection. The TURNkey risk levels would be considered by the business organisation against specific operational (and potentially business) risk scenarios and the specific risks to the business organisation would be identified. Depending upon the business organisations risk tolerance (note: it is likely that the same business organisation would have different risk tolerances for different business activities) HR would place critical repair teams (which may involve employees undertaking different roles to their normal role) on standby alert. Logistics/transport manager would also initiate transport management plans to ensure that key members of repair teams could make their way to site. Emergency response teams would be called to site before ground shaking starts. Maintenance inspection teams will be called the site once ground shaking ceases.</p>
Primary Actor:	The business continuity manager responsible for post event recovery.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The business continuity manager; • All related business/production/maintenance managers; • Individual employees; • Facilities management (security, catering); • The organisations health and safety manager who monitors risk levels; • Family of emergency response team; • The TURNkey system who wants to issue reliable forecasts.
Preconditions:	<p>Real time updates of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties, showing seismic hazard and risk to assets. An earthquake forecast (green, yellow, amber, red) has been issued with an associated timeframe (e.g., red forecast for the next 48 hours).</p>
Success guarantee:	Appropriate repair teams are on site to start the post event recovery process as soon as the forecast level has returned to green.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) OEF received by the business organisation via civil protection (this could be push notification, pull notification or both). 2) Disaster response (and coordination) and repair teams are notified of the potential for ground shaking and confirm their expected location at the predicted time. 3) Managers responsible for coordinating physical inspection of critical business organisation systems have pre-programmed work tasks for the initial inspection teams.

	<p>4) Detailed repair teams are transported to site as inspection teams identify faults.</p> <p>5) Logistics teams (warehouse, security, catering etc) are transported to site.</p>
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<p>1) Red OEF issued.</p> <p>2) No ground shaking occurs.</p> <p>3) Business organisation incurs financial loss (although this was not considered to be a major concern for most interviewees - it was heavily outweighed by their sense of corporate social responsibility).</p>
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<p>1) No forecast is received.</p> <p>2) Ground shaking occurs.</p> <p>3) Recovery is delayed because repair teams are not prepared for.</p> <p>4) Business organisation and employee lose confidence in the system.</p>

8.3.2.2 UC: activating off-site backup

TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., ‘red alert for the next 48 hours’). It is not technically feasible to give an end time. TURNkey will not provide OEF directly to critical infrastructure providers and businesses, but indirectly – via civil protection.

Table 36 UC: activating off-site backup – instance 1: physical assets

Goal:	To test the readiness of off-site backup systems prior to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	<p>Instance 1 (physical assets):</p> <p>To achieve this goal, the TURNkey Platform will issue OEF's of an increased likelihood of ground shaking over a pre-determined time period real time updates of changes in seismic hazard for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG system – red, amber, green). The OEF would be in the form of risk levels (green – no increased risk level, yellow, amber, red). TURNkey will notify critical infrastructure providers and general businesses of changes in risk to their assets. It will do so indirectly, via civil protection for the primary and backup business locations. The TURNkey risk levels would be considered by the business organisation against specific operational (and potentially business) risk scenarios and the specific risks to the business organisation would be identified. Depending upon the business organisations risk tolerance (note: it is likely that the same business organisation would have different risk tolerances for different business activities). Business managers would activate backup location operations plans (testing all physical systems, checking relocation plans, engaging additional logistics as required, issuing advice to employees of a potential change in working location, etc). Senior business managers will evaluate the potential risks. Senior business managers would either initiate a redeployment before ground shaking starts, or develop rapid redeployment plans that could be initiated once ground shaking had stopped.</p>
Primary Actor:	Senior business managers.

Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Senior business manager; • Related business managers who may be affected by relocation (e.g., warehouse manager, production manager, logistics manager etc); • The organisations health and safety manager who monitors risk levels; the TURNkey system who wants to issue reliable forecasts.
Preconditions:	<p>Real time updates of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties, showing seismic hazard and risk to assets.</p> <p>An earthquake forecast (green, yellow, amber, red) has been issued with an associated timeframe (e.g., red forecast for the next 48 hours).</p>
Success guarantee:	Business disruption is minimised through a smooth and efficient activation of alternate off-site facilities.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) OEF received by the business organisation via civil protection (this could be push notification, pull notification or both). 2) Senior business managers convene their disaster management and business continuity response team who evaluate the risk level. 3) Other managers who are affected by the potential change of location ensure that their colleagues are aware of the circumstances and are prepared for a possible relocation of activities. 4) Inspection and testing of alternative location is initiated and preparations made to relocate physical and human assets if required. 5) OEFs are monitored and if business risk thresholds are passed relocation plans activated. 6) OEFs are monitored for potential after-shocks and when OEF returns to green business activities return to the primary location.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Red OEF issued. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) Business organisation incurs significant financial loss. 4) Business organisation loses confidence in the system.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No forecast is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) Significant disruption occurs to the business operations. 4) Business organisation and employee loses confidence in the system.

TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., ‘red alert for the next 48 hours’). It is not technically feasible to give an end time. TURNkey will not provide OEF directly to critical infrastructure providers and businesses, but indirectly – via civil protection.

Table 37 UC: activating off-site backup – instance 2: data assets

Goal:	To test the readiness of off-site backup systems prior to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	Instance 2 (data assets): To achieve this goal, the TURNkey Platform will issue OEF's of an increased likelihood of ground shaking over a pre-determined time period real time updates of changes in seismic hazard for a

	<p>specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG system – red, amber, green). The OEF would be in the form of risk levels (green—no increased risk level, yellow, amber, red). TURNkey will notify critical infrastructure providers and general businesses of changes in risk to their assets. It will do so indirectly, via civil protection for the primary and backup business locations. The TURNkey risk levels would be considered by the business organisation against specific operational (and potentially business) risk scenarios and the specific risks to the business organisation would be identified. Depending upon the business organisations risk tolerance (note: it is likely that the same business organisation would have different risk tolerances for different business activities). Business managers would activate data asset backup location operations plans.</p>
Primary Actor:	Senior IT manager.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Senior business managers; • The TURNkey system who wants to issue reliable, detailed, forecasts.
Preconditions:	<p>Real time updates of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties, showing seismic hazard and risk to assets. An earthquake forecast (green, yellow, amber, red) has been issued with an associated timeframe (e.g., red forecast for the next 48 hours).</p>
Success guarantee:	Business disruption is minimised through a smooth and efficient backup of data assets.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) OEF received by the business organisation via civil protection (this could be push notification, pull notification or both). 2) Senior business managers convene their disaster management and business continuity response team who evaluate the risk level. 3) IT manager instigates of site data asset backup.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Red OEF issued. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) Business organisation incurs some financial loss. 4) Business organisation loses confidence in the system.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No forecast is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) Significant disruption occurs to the business operations. 4) Business organisation and employee lose confidence in the system.

8.3.2.3 UC: relocation of temporary/portable logistics equipment to business vulnerable sites

TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., ‘red alert for the next 48 hours’). It is not technically feasible to give an end time. TURNkey will not provide OEF directly to critical infrastructure providers and businesses, but indirectly – via civil protection.

Table 38 UC: relocation of temporary/portable logistics equipment to business vulnerable sites

Goal:	To increase the speed of recovery of vulnerability assets to ground shaking.
Use Case Instance:	To achieve this goal, the TURNkey Platform will issue OEF's of an increased likelihood of ground shaking over a pre-determined time period real time updates of changes in seismic hazard for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG system – red, amber, green). The OEF would be in the form of risk levels (green – no increased risk level, yellow, amber, red). TURNkey will notify critical infrastructure providers and general businesses of changes in risk to their assets. It will do so indirectly, via civil protection for the primary and backup business locations. The TURNkey risk levels would be considered by the business organisation against specific operational (and potentially business) risk scenarios and the specific risks to the business organisation would be identified. Depending upon the business organisations risk tolerance (note: it is likely that the same business organisation would have different risk tolerances for different business activities). Business managers (or specialist subcontractors) would redeploy portable systems (e.g., portable generators) to sites where loss of power was identified as a specific vulnerability following ground shaking. Redeployments of portable systems to individual sites would be prioritised to reflect the impact that the loss (or partial loss) of functionality of the site would have on the overall business.
Primary Actor:	Senior business manager/specialist subcontractor responsible for the site.
Stakeholders and Interests:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Senior business manager/specialist subcontractor; • Related business managers who may be affected by relocation (e.g., managers of similar sites, disaster/business continuity manager, etc); • The TURNkey system who wants to issue reliable forecasts.
Preconditions:	Real time updates of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties, showing seismic hazard and risk to assets. An earthquake forecast (green, yellow, amber, red) has been issued with an associated timeframe (e.g., red forecast for the next 48 hours).
Success guarantee:	Business disruption is minimised through rapid recovery of the functionality of a site following ground shaking.
Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) OEF received by the business organisation via civil protection (this could be push notification, pull notification or both). 2) Senior business managers convene their disaster management and business continuity response team who evaluate the risk level. 3) The redeployments of portable logistics equipment to priority critical sites is initiated. 4) On arrival at this site the portable equipment is installed and tested. 5) A state of readiness is reported back to senior business managers.
Alternate scenario –	1) Red OEF issued.

False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) Business organisation incurs some financial loss. 4) Business organisation loses confidence in the system.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No forecast is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) Significant disruption occurs to the business operations. 4) Business organisation and employee lose confidence in the system.

8.3.3 Prevention of cascading hazard events

TURNkey cannot issue forecasts/warnings with an associated timeframe (e.g., ‘red alert for the next 48 hours’). It is not technically feasible to give an end time. TURNkey will not provide OEF directly to critical infrastructure providers or businesses, but indirectly – via civil protection. TURNkey will not facilitate a way for organizations to share OEF with their critical business partners by the end of the project. However, there are no technical barriers preventing this from being realized in the future.

8.3.3.1 UC: Joint Planning

Table 39 UC: Joint Planning

Goal:	To reduce the impact of operational downtime on business customers (and the local economy)
Use Case Instance:	Instance 1: To achieve this goal, the TURNkey Platform will issue OEF's of an increased likelihood of ground shaking over a pre-determined time period real time updates of changes in seismic hazard for a specific location. This will take the form of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties (e.g., using the RAG system – red, amber, green). The OEF would be in the form of risk levels (green – no increased risk level, yellow, amber, red). TURNkey will notify critical infrastructure providers and general businesses of changes in risk to their assets. It will do so indirectly, via civil protection . The critical infrastructure provider – in partnership with key business customers - would consider the TURNkey risk levels against specific operational (and potentially business) risk scenarios. The specific risks to the CI's service / product delivery would be identified. Depending upon their shared assessment of the risk (which may differ for different business activities) the CI and its core business customers would jointly plan for different scenarios (or revise and update existing planning).
Primary Actor:	The risk manager at the critical infrastructure provider.
Stakeholders and Interests:	Senior management at the CI and business customer, risk management, operational management, warehousing and distribution, logistics (etc); the TURNkey system who wants to issue reliable forecasts.
Preconditions:	Real time updates of easy-to-read forecasts/warnings with associated uncertainties, showing seismic hazard and risk to assets. An earthquake forecast (green, yellow, amber, red) has been issued with an associated timeframe (e.g., red forecast for the next 48 hours).
Success guarantee:	The impact on business customers (and the local economy) of CI's operational downtime is significantly less than if no action had been taken.

Main success scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) OEF received by critical infrastructure provider via civil protection, which it shares with and its core business customers (this could be push notification, pull notification or both). 2) If the risk level is above a previously agreed threshold, the risk managers at the CI and its business customer review the forecast during a call. 3) If deemed necessary, a meeting is organised whereby the CI and its core business customers jointly plan for different scenarios (or revise and update existing planning). 4) Other managers who are affected by what is decided are made aware.
Alternate scenario – False-Positive alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Red OEF issued. 2) No ground shaking occurs. 3) CI and business customer have developed or reviewed joint mitigation plans – that are not needed on this occasion.
Alternate scenario – False-Negative alert	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No forecast is received. 2) Ground shaking occurs. 3) The business continuity of core customers is affected, which could have been avoided if joint mitigation plans had been developed or reviewed. 4) The critical infrastructure provider and its business customers lose confidence in the system.